

D3.2: Report on project standards

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1 Executive Summary

ARIADNE needs to identify the datasets and collections held by project partners which are available for integration, the metadata standards and database structures adopted by those datasets, existing mappings between datasets and thesauri and controlled vocabularies, and any existing multilingual mappings which are available.

Deliverable 3.1 focuses on the metadata standards and thesauri which are available within the domain as a whole. Deliverable D3.2 describes those that are already in use within the consortium. A survey was undertaken to collect information about datasets, metadata standards and controlled vocabularies and thesauri, and a workshop was held in Pisa in November 2013 to help the workpackage leaders to draw conclusions from the initial data collection exercise.

The survey revealed a large quantity of data available for integration, but also the heterogeneous nature of much of this data. Several partners hold large collections of datasets of diverse structure, whilst other partners hold single datasets of identical structure. Using the metadata registry tool being developed by ARIADNE it is now clear that the project should be able to develop a catalogue of existing datasets and collections held by project partners, with the scope for addition of datasets held by others. Such a catalogue will provide an invaluable tool for resource discovery for European archaeological researchers. In addition, the survey and workshop also revealed several areas for potential integration of collection at item level, as discussed in Section 6, including grey literature reports and records of sites and monuments. It also became clear that many research queries focus on issues of What, When and Where, and that in many cases the metadata held by partners is sufficient to support these searches.

The results of the survey of project partners datasets, metadata standards and vocabularies provides invaluable information which will inform the implementation of the project's metadata registry and will help the project to plan for ingestion. The datasets that have been identified provide the starting point.

The wide very range of content types that have been identified, their specialist nature and complexity confirms the need for ARIADNE to adopt a rich ontology to support their integration into the project infrastructure. The CIDOC-CRM can provide such an ontology.

2 Introduction

The main objective of ARIADNE WP3 is to compile a registry of metadata schemas, vocabularies and other standards that are relevant with the Archaeology domain and used by the project's partners, as well as any mappings between them. Due to the large number of standards currently in use, the registry will provide an interoperability platform for the research community. The registry will follow the metadata registry standards, such as ISO 11179 and the framework defined by the DESIRE and ROADS projects.

The aim of the first task of the workpackage, Task 3.1, is to survey currently used data standards used by the research community together with any available bilateral mapping. The survey carried out an extensive analysis of the literature, both on-line and off-line, and directly contacting institutions using those standards if necessary for further information. This survey is reported under the parallel Deliverable D3.1.

The second task, Task 3.2, aims to document the metadata schemas for the ARIADNE's Integrated Infrastructure. Moreover it will also define policies for data access, keeping into account the

requirements defined by the owners of rights on the data (to be reported in Deliverable D3.3). Such policies will comply with the EU strategic policies of Open Access to Data.

Finally the third task, Task 3.3, focuses on domain vocabularies and thesauri and surveys and document existing solutions for interoperability, including multilingual aspects. It also considers on gazetteers and other reference lists.

This deliverable presents the results of a survey aiming to collect information about (i) the collections and datasets held by the ARIADNE project partners, as well as (ii) the metadata standards and (iii) vocabularies specifically used by them. The information provided is valuable because:

- it indicates the standards adopted by the project partners
- makes evident the heterogeneity of the information which will be integrated within the data model of the ARIADNE registry
- it is useful for the estimation of the volume of the holdings of ARIADNE registry and hence for the design and implementation of the registry functionalities and services

3 Data collection strategy

The data presented in this report were collected by means of a questionnaire sent to all ARIADNE content providing partners. The questionnaire is attached in Appendix F. All partners involved in this workpackage replied in detail, so the present report provides a complete overview of datasets to be integrated in ARIADNE, as known at the present time.

Partners' datasets will be recorded in the project Registry with complete information on metadata structure, quantity of records or other size measure, and so on.

The present survey is a snapshot of the datasets planned for integration taken at the date of the report's compilation, and provides the information necessary for proceeding with integration and services design. Nonetheless it is envisaged that the Registry will be a comprehensive and continuously updated database, progressively extended to include other datasets outside of the project consortium, including those owned by institutions willing to co-operate with ARIADNE.

4 Datasets and collections of data in the ARIADNE consortium

The responses to the survey reveal that the data owned by partners are organized in diverse formats including databases, collections (i.e. flat file sets) of images, text, 3D, CAD, video, and as GIS. This section provides a description of the content that the members of the project consortium plan to make available for ingestion to ARIADNE.

ADS

The datasets held by the Archaeology Data Service [1] include:

- Over one million Archsearch metadata records
- Over 20.000 Grey Literature reports (with DC extended metadata), which could be used for data mining

- Over 400 individual archives, consisting of reports, data, images and a variety of other primary resources resulting from archaeological research; resource discovery metadata (extended Dublin Core) for the archives is also available as RDF from ADS Linked Data endpoint
- A selected group of archives that have been mapped to the CRM-EH ontology, and are available as RDF served from ADS Linked Data endpoint

Content covers all archaeological subjects and all the archaeological periods (aligned to the MIDAS periods list along with date range when possible) primarily about UK, but also archaeological work carried out by UK archaeologists worldwide is included. Data format include: CAD (SVG, DXF), databases (delimited text), GIS (shapefiles), images (raster), video (MPG, AVI), spreadsheets (CSV), text (PDF/A), statistics (delimited text), VR/Video (MPG, AVI, MOV, FLV/WRL), geophysics/survey (DAT, DZT, GSI, raster), audio (MP3).

In detail, as of today the content provided by ADS includes:

- 248,072 Image files (raster)
- 55,247 PDF
- 2,283 Text
- 2,616 CAD/Vector (SVG, DXF)
- 9,324 XLS/CSV Spreadsheets
- 581 MPG/AVI/MOV/FLV/WRL VR/Video
- 70 MP3 Audio
- 150 DBF/MDB Databases
- 689 DAT/DZT/GSI Geophysics/Survey
- 936 SBN/PRJ/SBX/SHX/XYZTFW GIS
- 3145 HTML/CSS/XML

KNAW-DANS

The Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS) of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Science (KNAW) will make available to the project two datasets: EDNA and DCCD.

The Dutch archaeology e-depot (EDNA) is accommodated at DANS and stores the digital files with research data of Dutch archaeologists. These are the files with the primary archaeological data of excavations, regional explorations and material studies. It notably concerns completed and published research results, of which the author(s) has (have) made the basic data accessible to other scientists. Both the research descriptions and all data can be downloaded via the archiving system EASY.

Over 1,561,838 data files are stored in the archaeological part of EASY collection. These files consists of:

- Over 17,000 reports in PDF and described with the same metadata schema (single files)
- Over 3,000 large datasets (individual archives) consisting of text documents, images (photos and scans), GIS, CAD, data tables.

Content, mainly in Dutch and in some cases in English, covers all archaeological periods, primarily about the Netherlands, but also archaeological work carried out by Dutch Archaeologists worldwide is included.

DANS preferred formats are PDF/A, CSV, MID/MIF, DXF, SVG, JPG and TIFF. Data is requested in DANS preferred formats, therefore if deposited in acceptable formats (DOC, RTF, ODT, XLS, ODS, MDB, ACCDB, DBF, TAB, SHP, DWG, AI, EPS, various image formats) the data will be converted to the corresponding preferred formats.

Original data in non-preferred formats is archived but not published.

Digital Collaboratory for Cultural Dendrochronology (DCCD) is an international digital data library for dendrochronology whose content (a trusted digital repository at DANS) consists of more than 50,000 series of tree-ring measurements (ca. 350,000 annual observations) from 4000 projects, average tree-ring chronologies and descriptive and interpretative metadata (e.g., object and timber type, wood species, absolute calendar dates of the growth rings, provenance of the wood, et cetera) [2].

The DCCD is the only archaeological/historical tree-ring (meta)data network existing in Europe, which became operational in 2011. In the DCCD, Belgian, Danish, Dutch, English, French, German, Latvian, Lithuanian, Polish, and Spanish laboratories have joined data in a manner that suits their shared and individual research agendas. In its present state the DCCD contains more than 50,000 measurement series of different wood species derived from ca. 5,300 objects and sites dating between 6000 BC and present. Most data sets are described by very detailed metadata according to the newly developed international dendrochronological data standard TRiDaS (Jansma et al. 2010), amongst others using non-hierarchical multi-lingual controlled vocabularies (EN, FR, DE, NL). Ca. 50% of the DCCD collection is derived from archaeological sites and structures, including maritime archaeological sites. The remaining data are mostly historical as well, being derived from historical architecture and mobile heritage (paintings, furniture). The content is available as JPG, MPEG, Quicktime, HTML, PDF etc.

The measurement data and metadadata in XML files refers to the TRiDaS Standard (<http://www.tridas.org/>). Original measurement files for dendrochronology are available in text and binary formats and project reports in pdf.

DAI

The German Archaeological Institute will provide ARIADNE with the dataset iDAI.images/ARACHNE [3]. It focuses on Roman and Greek antiquity, but extends its scope to all fields of archaeological investigation done by the DAI. It covers the Mediterranean areas from Prehistory until Late Antiquity.

ARACHNE originally started as a picture database exclusively for ancient sculpture with images from photo campaigns done in museums. Later on the entire picture archives of the departments of the DAI had joint in this project and contributed images from fieldwork etc. ARACHNE therefore also contains images from several other projects:

1. Images: glass negatives digitized, implemented by using CRM and integrated in other web resources
2. iDAI.Bookbrowser, Reception of Antiquity in a Semantic Network: engraved prints from the 16th and 19th century visible and searchable by the TEI-Viewer offering metadata, OCR and further links
3. The Berlin Sculpture-Network: online catalogue of the Antiquities Collection of the SBM (State Museums of Berlin) with about 2,600 objects accessible
4. Digitale Fototheken, Fotothek DAI Istanbul, Fotothek DAI Kairo, Fotothek DAI Madrid, Fotothek DAI Rom (Skulpturenegative DAI ROM, Nachlass Josef Röder, Inventarbücher [Find aids], Fotothek DAI Zentrale, Fotothek DAI Orientabteilung)

The content mostly consists of images in JPEG, TIFF and text in xml available in Latin and Greek. ARACHNE contains:

- 1,7 million images registered of which 1.400.000 are visible for everyone
- approximately 11.000 registered users can access 700.000 book pages in about 3.650 books as well as 220.000 objects and buildings and 20.000 topographies
- contextualization given by approximately 3.200.000 relations between ARACHNE records

ATHENA RC – CETI

The Cultural and Educational Technology Institute of the ‘Athena’ – Research and Innovation Centre in Information, Communication and Knowledge Technologies institutes will contribute to the project a database of Chemical analysis and dating data of ceramic sherds and clays

Clay Database contains numerical data (ASCII), text (PDF), images e.g. pictures, diagrams, plots (JPG) proprietary binary file formats from scientific software packages of approximately 1500 ceramic sherds from Northern and western Greece, from Geometric until Byzantine period. Content is available in Greek and English but currently not all fields have the corresponding English translation.

DISCOVERY

The Discovery Programme will provide ARIADNE infrastructure with four datasets.

WODAN is an online integrated wood and charcoal database with results from Irish archaeological sites [4]. Data includes works at multiple granularity levels including site, sample information and individual palaeo-environmental fragment details. The content consist of text in English, with some associated images and it refers to Ireland and Northern Ireland covering multi periods. Data is available in online MySQL database, and also contains associated pdf, excel and word document: 533 archaeological sites, 2,849 charcoal sample records and 2,133 wood sample records.

Mapping Death facilitates access to a detailed database of burials and burial sites in Ireland from 1st to 8th century AD including archaeological, onomastic, statistical, mapping and historical data [5]. Generally data are texts with some associated images, scientific reports and laboratory data in English. The content, available as online MySQL database, concerns human remains, artefacts, monuments, osteology, C14 and isotope data from 174 excavations where human remains were discovered. The database also contains associated pdf, excel and word document.

Irish Stone Axe Project (ISAP) Database - The Irish Stone Axe Project (ISAP) has worked over twenty years to compile and make available a comprehensive record of all Irish stone within a project database. The subjects of the database are artefacts, petrology, and lithic tools of Ireland, Northern Ireland plus selected areas of UK Prehistory.

The project database contains records on over 21,000 stone axeheads. This covers contextual, location and spatial data, the morphological characteristics of the object and a petrological identification (including the results of a programme of microscopic petrological identification and geochemical analysis. The text record is accompanied by drawings (over 3,000) and by photographs of both axes and thin sections (500 plus). The database is regarded as setting a best practice international standard in stone axe studies. It is available an online MySQL database, which also contains associated JPG images [6].

SHARE-IT (Spatial Heritage Archaeological Research Environment using IT) consists of series of web mapping services derived from different remote sensing activities with archaeology research or cultural heritage management including lidar, geophysics and aerial archaeological surveys (approximately 50 individual surveys). All content is geospatially positioned to high degree of accuracy for use within GIS,

and it includes all periods covering Northern Ireland. Language is English. It includes a range of web-services depending upon content type compliant to ISO 11919:

- a. Web Feature Services (WFS) – survey extent data
- b. Web Mapping Services (WMS) - aerial imagery (ortho-images), and selected visualizations from lidar data (e.g. hillshades)
- c. Web Coverage Services (WCS) – geophysical data

It is anticipated that in addition to the described datasets other datasets will become available by external content providers through hosting by the Discovery Programme during the period of the ARIADNE project. However, at present no firm commitments have been made and the possibility will be explored with external content providers in 2013-2014 through focused workshops in Ireland.

SND

The Swedish National Data Service (SND) will provide ARIADNE with a GIS dataset of excavation data from the county of Östergötland, Sweden from the Stone Age to 19th century. The dataset consists of 361 pdf-files (reports), 386 shape-files (ESRI-GIS) and 355 access databases (MDB) [7]. Not all content is published yet.

ZRC- SAZU

The Scientific Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Science and Arts (ZRC-SAZU) will make two databases of archaeological sites and finds available to the ARIADNE infrastructure ZBIVA and ARKAS.

ZBIVA is an archaeological database of Early Medieval sites in the South-Eastern Alps. It covers sites in Slovenia, Austria, on the NW Croatian coast, and in the site in Italy in the NE regions, which are sometimes compared to sites from the neighbouring areas and the previous era.

The database consists of three parts (which together form a coherent unit):

- Sites database
- Graves database
- Objects database

The databases are trilingual (Slovenian, English, German). A version has been online since 2001 and provides sites data with the literature concerning each site, based on Libera, a database for literature on Early Middle Ages [8]. It is a relational database, originating in the mid-eighties with a structure unchanged since then, with ca. 3,000 items in html and MDB format and 5,500 images in various formats.

In addition to its archaeological dataset ZRC-SAZU will provide ARKAS [9] which comprises four subject areas: the first defines the sites according to place, content and length of time protected, the second the level of research work and protection, the third the sources of information, and the fourth the selected documentation kept by the Institute of Archaeology. It is a relational database, originating from the mid-nineties which structure remained unchanged, with data of Slovenia from Palaeolithic to Middle Age. The approximately 9000 items are mostly GIS location and text in Slovenian, in the format of html, MDB, JPG, gif.

MNM-NOK

The Hungarian National Museum National Heritage Protection Center will contribute datasets about archaeology, excavation, field survey and documentation covering the territory of Hungary from Paleolithic to early modern age. In particular:

Dataset of archaeological sites. The datasets contain field survey reports and documentation of more than 3000 sites, geophysical survey reports of more than 50 sites (reports, .shp files, .gpx files, photos, maps), text, GIS files of archaeological sites and excavations, drawings and photos of finds in the following formats: TIFF, JPG, PDF, MDB, XLS, DOC, DWG, SHP, GPX.

Dataset of scientific analyses. The collection includes more than 550 scientific analyses. The content consists of grey literature, reports of scientific analyses on ceramics, human and animal bones, glass, metal, stone tools, textile, wood, organic materials/food remains, phytolith, other archaeobotanical remains, 14C dating, environmental reconstruction. This collection also includes papers and books of the already published results, text, GIS files of archaeological sites and excavations, drawings and photos of finds.

Excavation datasets composed of:

1st dataset: short reports and maps of excavations

2nd dataset: Grey literature in Hungarian

It consists of a complete documentation of archaeological excavations (excavation report, maps of sites and features, feature descriptions, description of stratigraphical units, list of the excavated periods according to features, feature photos, photo inventories, GPS coordinates of the excavated area, feature drawings, inventory of drawings, find inventory, drawings and photos of finds, documentation of restoration). This collection also includes papers and books of the already published sites. Reports and documentation are already available for 1038 excavations (and constantly rising). GIS files of archaeological sites and excavations, drawings and photos of finds. Formats: TIFF, JPG, PDF, MDB, XLS, DOC, DWG, SHP, GPX.

CyI-STARC

The Science and Technology in Archaeology Research Center of the Cyprus Institute will contribute datasets of Archaeology and Cultural Heritage of Cyprus, Israel and Italy from Bronze Age to 20th century AD:

- Famagusta Gate
- Paphos Theatre
- Agios Georgios Hill
- Byzantine Museum
- Hala Sultan Tekke
- Cyprus Folk Art Museum
- Art Gallery
- The Cyprus Museum

The dataset [10] varies in terms of chronological periods and context and the content consists of:

- 2D images of archaeological sites and artifacts (2193)
- 3D PDFs of archaeological artifacts and archaeological sites (324)
- Texts regarding excavation diaries, both in Greek and in English

Data format provided: JPG, PNG, 3D PDF, XML

ARUP-CAS

The Institute of Archaeology of the Academy of Science (AS) of the Czech Republic in Prague will contribute to the project with the Archaeological map of the Czech Republic – aerial archaeology (AA AMCR).

Archaeological Map of the Czech Republic (AMCR) is a complex database system joining an on-line registration of archaeological field interventions on the territory of Bohemia with the information on their results, digital archives of excavation reports, bibliography, etc. from the Neolithic to 20th century. One important component of the AMCR is a database of aerial archaeology, which consists of aerial archaeology, archaeological sites, sites and monuments records, historic monuments and aerial photography. The content is available in Czech, but may be translated to English. It consists of 10,000 digital photographs (JPG); GIS information layers (SHP); and a database (MDB).

OEAW

The Prehistoric Commission of the Austrian Academy of Science (ÖAW) will provide the following databases for integration to ARIADNE.

Franzhausen Kokoron is a MS Access database, containing tables with information about Late Bronze Age (1050-800 BC) graves and their finds: i.e. pottery and bones. The 3,827 data sets consist of text (in German) and images (MDB and JPG), covering areas of KG Franzhausen, Lower Austria. An online version provides additional image data [11].

UK Material-POOL is a MS Access Database containing information about Late Bronze Age settlements (urnfield culture) in Austria and information about the status of analysis regarding these settlements. The 442 data set entries (MDB) consist of text in German [12].

Fundprotokoll Thunau Scan a MS Access database is under development and contains image data (scans of analogue find drawings) including all find categories, except ceramics, of a Late Bronze Age and medieval settlement of Thunau am Kamp, Lower Austria. The data input is based on the excavation register. About 74,000 entries consist of text (MDB) with hyperlinks to the images and images (tiff).

AIAC

The International Association of Classical Archaeology will make available to ARIADNE two datasets.

FOLD&R (Fasti On Line Documents & Research) [13], is an on-line peer-reviewed journal containing reports, both preliminary and final, on Italian excavations from 2000 onwards. Up to date it counts more than 286 images and text (pdf) written in Italian and covering all archaeological periods.

FASTI Online is a site and intervention (excavation, geophysical, survey, etc.) summary records across the Mediterranean [14]. It includes more than 5000 site/season records of excavations in Italy, Serbia, Bulgaria, Romania, Macedonia, Malta, Morocco, Croatia, Albania, Slovenia, Kosovo, Montenegro, Ukraine and it covers all archaeological periods. It contains text (summaries) with metadata associated with site/intervention summaries, images, and links to online videos (held elsewhere). Data format are JPG, PDF, HTML.

Summaries are provided in at least 2 languages depending on country (language of origin and english) including: Italian, Serbian, Bulgarian, Romanian, Macedonian, Maltese, French, Arabic, Croatian, Russian, Albanian, Slovenian, Ukrainian, Spanish.

NIAM-BAS

The National Institute of Archaeology with Museum of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences will provide the Archaeological Map of Bulgaria dataset to ARIADNE.

Archaeological Map of Bulgaria. Conceived almost two decades ago, the dataset was designed with two major purposes: to collect reports from archaeological sites and to prepare data for a map and geographical database of the archaeological objects and activities in Bulgaria. Initial data collection focussed on activity reports and this functionality was extended. During the last few years, geographical data was collected into the database; preparation for more extensive geographical data collection is in progress. The dataset [15] has a limited access protected by an issue released in 2011 by the Bulgarian Ministry of Culture, but the process of preparing an open access version with non-sensitive information is in progress.

The content consists of a database (SQLite), images (maps, plans and various illustrative material in JPG, PNG and GIF images), documents with additional information (optionally uploaded by users, mostly in DOC and PDF formats – available only for a very small fraction of the entries).

Content is available in Bulgarian and multiple nomenclatures are used for the majority of the information collected, which can be translated with moderate effort. The total amount of data is ca. 17000. About 5000 items are more recent and recorded with the latest nomenclature and options (e.g. images, coordinates etc.). The rest is being corrected and amended.

MiBACT-ICCU

The Central Institute for the Union Catalogue of Italian Libraries, which represents in ARIADNE the Italian Ministry of Cultural Heritage and Activities and Tourism (MiBACT), will provide the infrastructure with:

CulturalItalia aggregated dataset [16] is a metadata dataset of archaeological objects, in Italian and consists of text and images in JPG, from Palaeolithic to Middle Ages about the Italian territory.

CulturalItalia describes digital resources and physical resources pertaining to the whole cultural heritage domain using a specifically conceived Application Profile based on Dublin Core (PICO AP). Metadata are used to describe cultural resources both at item and at collection level. The DC PICO AP allows the integration and interoperability of data on different sectors of cultural heritage, with the overall objective to merge all these contributions into Europeana.

The archaeological dataset, composed of 52,193 metadata records with a preview image aggregate by CulturalItalia are from the following content providers:

- Regione Marche (17.121)
- MuseiD-Italia (15.790)
- Regione Lombardia (7.150)
- Regione Emilia Romagna (4.157)
- Direzione Regionale Campania (3.252)
- FOTOSAR (2.049)
- Direzione Regionale Lombardia (1.388)
- Regione Umbria (1.286)

General Information System for Cataloguing (SIGEC Web) is the national catalogue of archaeological heritage and architectural, artistic, ethno-anthropological, scientific-technical and natural heritage. It is divided into four modules: three of these totally control the descriptive, multimedia and geographic information, while the fourth is aimed at processing the data for its use on Internet, while guaranteeing

respect of rights of intellectual ownership, privacy and all necessary requirements for the safety of heritage.

Data consists of text, image, 3D, GIS location in Pdf, doc, odt, JPG, tiff, xls, MDB, dwg, dxf, shp, obj, fbx, from Palaeolithic to Middle Ages of the Italian territory.

Sistema Informativo Territoriale Archeologico di Roma (SITAR) is the Archaeological Territorial Information System of Rome, launched in 2007 and managed by the Soprintendenza Speciale per i Beni Archeologici di Roma (SSBAR), the Roma branch of the MiBACT. The system manages various types of data sets, ranging from large monumental contexts to single archaeological features found in rescue excavations, deriving from the entirety of salvage or planned investigations carried out in the territory of the Cities of Rome and Fiumicino, from Palaeolithic to contemporary period.

The underlying architecture of SITAR web platform is based on four primary information layers and some higher interpretative levels still under implementation:

1. Information Sources (in acronym OI, Origini dell'informazione): the administrative and scientific information of every single archaeological digging, geophysical/geological survey, topographical study, etc. (in others words the sources of information)
2. Archaeological Partitions (PA, Partizioni Archeologiche): the scientific description of the archaeological findings even if fragmentary, always identified by the binomial of chronological and functional criteria
3. Archaeological Units (UA, Unità Archeologiche): each archaeological complex or monument, conventionally identified by the logical union of many PA, which analysed together make an unambiguous archaeological monumental context (for example a specific ancient building)
4. Archaeological Restrictions (DT, Dispositivi di Vincolo): preservation restrictions affecting each complex and/or monument
5. Archaeological Potential, still in development: it is generated by the logic/semantic union and super-interpretation of the base layers. Local authorities and institutional bodies will share and integrate in its IDT/GIS systems the SITAR archaeological potential mapping tools to project and plan future developments of the urban contexts

The data in the SSBAR archive refer to excavations, field researches and territorial studies realized from about 1860 to 2013.

The datasets consist of text, image, 3D, GIS location, scientific documentation survey reports; cartographic, graphic and photographic documentation; multimedia contents; 3D models; etc.; all the texts are in Italian.

Size of content: 11.000 geoDB SITAR records (OI, PA, UA, DT); 100.000 digital contents, in Pdf, doc, odt, JPG, tiff, xls, MDB, avi, mov, dwg, dxf, shp, obj, fbx, PostgreSQL RDBMS, Map Guide OS Library resources (xml files for layers and map objects definitions and stylizations).

ARHEO

The Arheovest Timisoara Association will contribute three datasets:

- Survey data of archaeological sites (bronze age and medieval)
- Geo-physical data
- Analysis of ceramics from excavations

The content of the datasets consists of distribution maps of sites, description of archaeological sites from surveys, description of ceramics analysis, geo-physical and electro-magnetic data and it refers to the Romanian Bronze Age and medieval periods.

Data consist of maps, text descriptions of sites, database of alphanumerical data and images in Romanian and English, available as xls, JPG, dbase, Google maps [17].

INRAP

The French National Institute of Preventive Archaeological Research will contribute the following datasets to ARIADNE:

Archeozoom database makes available the locations and geo-coordinates of major preventive archaeology sites operated by INRAP and the excavations card index: location, archaeological periods, themes and associated media. It covers all archaeological time periods and it includes major archaeological operations conducted in France by INRAP from 2002 on, or by its forerunner AFAN (Association pour les Fouilles Archéologiques Nationales) before 2002.

The content consist of:

Open data:

- Geolocation (National Coordinate Reference Systems Lambert 93)
- Content database (excavations card index in HTML)

Each excavations card index (1100 archaeological sites are available) summarizes the information and artefacts collected on the field. It can be associated to documents (pdf), photographs (JPG), short films (< 10 minutes) or audio (mp3). The content language is all in French. These contents cannot be provided for broadcast on other sites than INRAP's online platforms due to copyright. They are freely accessible on Archeozoom platform [18], Images d'archéologie [19] and INRAP's website [20].

DOLIA (DOcumentation de L'InrAp) is a catalogue containing the scientific documentation created and used by INRAP. The main part is the "rapports d'opération" (archaeological operation reports) created by INRAP teams during preventive archaeological operations. Some parts of the document have been removed for legal issues and to insure protection of the sites. Other documents are progressively added to the collection:

- sets of document archives created during the archaeological operations (e.g. photographs, plans, catalogue of artefacts)
- any other documents related to archaeology in France, such as monographs or published articles

Each document is presented with a bibliographical record. The document itself may be available directly in PDF form or by giving its physical location within INRAP. The coverage includes all archaeological operations conducted in France by INRAP from 2002 on, or by its forerunner AFAN (Association pour les Fouilles Archéologiques Nationales) before 2002. All archaeological time periods are covered.

The content is available in French and consist of:

- 22.000 bibliographic records available with a public access
- 500 PDF documents available for external registered users
- Some photographs

Fonds Iconothèque – Images d'Archéologie (IDA) consists of 3380 documents of excavation sites of France and some foreign countries and covers all archaeological periods. The information recorded (in

excel) is available in French and concerns: reference, type of content (image, video, document), caption, periods, themes, situation, duration, date of creation, copyright, event, site, media type. In particular the open content associated consists of:

- 3000 photos, photographic reports and images (JPG, PNG)
- 150 printed documents (PDF)
- 230 videos (MOV, AVI, MP4)

5 Metadata schemas and vocabularies used in the project

5.1 Metadata schemas

5.1.1 Metadata standard or compliant to standards

This section provides a summary of the metadata standards which have actually been adopted by partners for compliance in their datasets. Each of these standards is described in more detail in the companion project deliverable, D3.1 [21].

KNAW-DANS has adopted the TRiDaS Standard [22] for the Digital Collaboratory for Cultural Dendrochronology (DCCD) dataset. Only fields from the TRiDaS Project and some of the TRiDaS Object information are publicly available.

For the Dutch archaeology e-depot (EDNA) KNAW-DANS has adopted Qualified Dublin Core including the following elements: Creator, Title, Description, Date Created, Access Rights, Date Available, Audience, Contributor, Subject, Spatial Coverage, Temporal Coverage, Source, Identifier, Format, Relation, Language, Remarks, Alternative Title, Rights Holder, Publisher, Type, Date plus the following extra drop-down fields (records):

- Subject-ABR T and Temporal-ABR
- Spatial point or spatial box (special fields for coordinates)
- Field for importing Archis number (of state agency)

DISCOVERY conforms to the EU INSPIRE directive [23] and ISO 11915 for SHARE-IT (Spatial Heritage Archaeological Research Environment using IT) and the INSPIRE theme list for its Spatial Data Themes.

SND uses the DDI standard for the dataset of GIS data from Östergötland (Sweden); this standard is compliant with ISO11179 and most parts of the ISO19000- family. In particular SND has adopted DD12.5, DD13.1, DC, DC terms, DataCite and MARC-XML.

MiBACT-ICCU uses the PICO Application profile [24] for its CulturalItalia aggregated dataset.

For the General Information System for Cataloguing' (SIGEC Web) MiBACT-ICCU has defined a set of standards including:

- **SI file** – Archaeological Site [25]
- **SAS file** – Stratigraphical Probe [26]
- **MA/CA file** - Archaeological Monument / Archaeological Complex [27]
- **RA file** – Archaeological Find [28]

- **NU file** – Numismatics [29]
- **TMA file** –Archaeological Materials Report [30]
- **AT file** – Anthropological Finds [31]

INRAP complies with the UNIMARC [32] schema for its DOLIA (DOcumentation de L’InrAp) dataset (attached in Appendix E).

5.1.2 Proprietary schemas

This section provides a summary of the proprietary schemas which have been developed by partners for use in their datasets.

ADS - The ADS Archive Metadata Schema is based on some of the metadata collected for each archive at the ADS. The schema is mostly aligned with the Collections Management System (CMS) used by the ADS to manage its archives. Below is a description of each metadata property or attribute, its data type, and the number of occurrences. UoY ADS Metadata Schema (attached in Appendix A).

DAI - ARACHNE is based on a relational database mysql with overall 177 tables. Data can be harvested via OAI-PMH in the original format, Qualified Dublin Core, CIDOC-CRM and TEI.

ATHENA RC – CETI has defined a proprietary schema for the Clay Database; metadata are currently available in Greek, which will be available soon translated into English.

DISCOVERY reported that there is no metadata explicitly created for its three databases but that the metadata could be harvested from the content within, i.e. site name, site type, geographical location (lat/Log).

For the integrate wood and charcoal database (WODAN) there are 68 fields within the Charcoal records and 106 fields within the wood record which could be used. This data has not been mapped to any schema.

For the Mapping Death database in totality there are 98 fields within the database which record a range of information within the categories Site details, cremation details, inhumation details, related publications, associated scientific data (C14 & isotope data) and associated media.

For the Irish Stone Axe Project (ISAP) Database the metadata could be harvested with the content within the database, i.e. excavation data, site name, site type, object type, geographical location (lat/Log). In totality there are 78 fields within the database, which record a range of information within the categories Site details, artifact and tooling data, petrology and excavation data.

ZRC SAZU has developed two proprietary metadata schema for their datasets ARKAS and ZBIVA (attached in Appendix B) with the bibliography in LIBERA.

MNM-NOK - Schemas are available only for excavation dataset, this contains: list of types, periods, material, condition and acquisition of objects. It is only for internal use, no widely accepted schema is available for Hungarian datasets so far.

CyI-STARC reported that it could provide metadata in three formats: 1) STARC metadata schema; 2) Customized LIDO metadata schema; and 3) CyInscription metadata schema.

ARUP-CAS reported that for the Archaeological Map of the Czech Republic – aerial archaeology (AA AMCR) a proprietary form is used, resulting from the long-term tradition of archaeological archiving in the IA and the CR. The database is structured into two main files (SITES and PHOTOS) with two

additional (supporting) files, COMPONENTS (= site parts) and FLIGHTS (information on individual flights). The detailed description of metadata is included in the AA_CR_metadata.xls. It reports that so far, the “site” list has been translated into English but other parts can be translated soon, if needed.

OEAW - Database structure provided.

AIAC - FASTI Online FOLD&R journal entries are given metadata in FASTI Online and will be provided as part of that data set. AIAC plans to map FASTI Online metadata to the CIDOC-CRM; this process is ongoing.

NIAM-BAS reports that its schema is proprietary and developed over 20 years based on a database schema. The records are in Hungarian. Translation and mapping to CIDOC CRM is not trivial and is not proposed in the list.

MIBACT-ICCU reported that for Sistema Informativo Territoriale Archeologico di Roma (SITAR) the following schemas are available:

- OI Origini dell’informazione/Source of Information (the administrative and scientific information)
- PA Partizione Archeologica/ Archaeological Partition (the description of the archaeological findings)
- UA Unità Archeologica /Archaeological Unit (the scientific description of each archaeological complex or monument)
- DT Dispositivi di Vincolo / Law restriction Decrees: the law constraints which punctually preserves each complex and/or monument

All the above standards are included in Appendix D.

ARHEO reported that its data are organized in databases and Google maps and no metadata forms are used.

INRAP reported that metadata was not available for its Archeozoom database and its Fonds Iconothèque – Images d’Archéologie (IDA).

5.2 Vocabularies

5.2.1 Standard vocabularies

KNAW-DANS uses a multi-lingual controlled vocabulary for DCCD, which contains terms for dendrochronology, archaeology, build heritage etc. This vocabulary is not published yet and it is available mainly in Western European languages: English, Dutch, French, German.

For EDNA KNAW-DANS uses the controlled vocabularies (Archaeological Basis Register ABR) developed by RCE. Currently the ABR of the RCE is updated, by building a thesaurus (adding descriptions to 2500 terms) and it is mainly in Dutch and partially in English [33].

DISCOVERY reported using a series of different controlled vocabularies.

WODAN

- Geographic place names are based on Irish place-names database (logainm.ie)
- Monument classification vocabularies is based upon Irish National Monuments Service monument list

- Wood species Taxon – uses classification based upon extension of the Tree of Life project [34]
- Soils & Geology use Geological Survey of Ireland classifications

Mapping Death

- Geographic place names based upon Irish place-names database (logainm.ie)
- Monument classification vocabularies based upon Irish National Monuments Service monument list
- Artifact classification based upon National Museum of Ireland (NMI) list

Irish Stone Axe Project (ISAP) Database

- Geographic place names based upon Irish place-names database (logainm.ie)
- Monument classification vocabularies based upon Irish National Monuments Service monument list
- Artifact classification based upon National Museum of Ireland (NMI) list
- Petrology based upon Irish Geological Survey classifications

SHARE-IT (Spatial Heritage Archaeological Research Environment using IT)

- Geographic place names based upon Irish place-names database (logainm.ie)
- Keywords use themes-GEMET v2.4 [35]
- Spatial Data Themes uses INSPIRE theme list

SND uses the ELSST (European Language Social Science Thesaurus) plus local vocabularies, which include, amongst other, the monument type vocabularies of the Swedish National Heritage Board (RAÄ). The local list is partially translated by SND into English. RAÄ plans to conduct a SKOSification of their vocabularies, which will be used in the future by SND. The vocabulary is in Swedish and partially in English, due to on-going translation process.

ARUP-CAS - The AA database uses standardized thesauri, which have been developed within the ARIADNE project. It is anticipated they will be translated from Czech into English to enable an international access to AA data on-line.

MiBACT-ICCU uses the PICO Thesaurus for the CulturalItalia aggregated dataset. PICO is available in Italian [36].

For the General Information System for Cataloguing' (SIGEC Web) controlled vocabularies are available for: archaeological objects/finds; archaeological sites; and numismatics [37-41].

Sistema Informativo Territoriale Archeologico di Roma (SITAR)

For the Origini dell'Informazione / Sources of Information:

- SITAR vocabularies: Acquisition methodologies; Georeferencing degrees; Georeferencing methods; Representation degrees; Legal Persons; Natural Persons; SSBAR Officers; SSBAR administrative zones & services
- ISTAT (Italian statistics agency), Municipality of Rome and of Fiumicino vocabulary: Toponym zones and Localities
- Agenzia del Territorio (Italian cadaster agency): Toponym street registry

For the Partizioni Archeologiche / Archaeological Partitions:

- SITAR vocabularies: PA type; Objective Definition; Specific Definition (based on the ICCD MA-CA model thesaurus, work in progress by the SITAR workgroup), Interpretative Definition (corresponding to UA Specific Definition lexicon); Georeferencing degrees; Georeferencing methods; Representation degrees; Chronological intervals; Named year ranges (for historical periods and sub-periods)
- Buildings Techniques (and its constitutive elements): Working Group on the Repertoire of the Building Techniques of the Roman World

For the Unità Archeologiche / Archaeological Units:

- SITAR vocabularies: UA type; Objective Definition; Specific Definition; Georeferencing degrees; Georeferencing methods; Representation degrees; Chronological intervals; Named year ranges (for historical periods and sub-periods)
- Buildings Techniques (and its constitutive elements)

For the Dispositivi di Tutela / Law restriction Decrees:

- SITAR vocabularies: Relevant legislations; Restriction & conservation type; Decree type; Immovable cadastral type; Property type; Legal Persons; Natural Persons; SSBAR Officers; SSBAR administrative zones & services
- ISTAT (Italian statistical agency), Municipality of Rome and of Fiumicino vocabulary: Toponymic zones and Localities
- Agenzia del Territorio (Italian cadaster agency): Toponymic street registry

For the Digital Object:

- SITAR vocabularies: Document type

The above-listed forms are planned to be translated in English.

INRAP reported that four of the six Pactols thesauri from Frantiq network are used in DOLIA: Places, People, Chronology and Subject.

No vocabularies are adopted by INRAP for the other two databases: Archeozoom database and Description – Fonds Iconothèque – Images d’Archéologie (IDA)

5.2.2 Proprietary word lists

The following partners adopt for their datasets proprietary vocabularies or list of terms. In particular:

ADS developed a word list (attached in Appendix A).

DAI reported that ARACHNE makes use of many controlled word list especially designed for this database. Matching to the following vocabularies are available:

1. GND (Gemeinsame Normdatei) [42], especially used for named entities of persons
2. Geonames, the DAI is in the process of restructuring its authority files and just recently established a new gazetteer, iDAI.gazetteer [43]

ZRC-SAZU adopts a proprietary vocabulary in Slovenian.

MNM-NOK adopts for its datasets a vocabulary in Hungarian, which is only for internal use.

CyI-STARC is currently working on the creation of vocabularies and terminologies fitting the research work of the center to be available both in English and Greek.

AIAC developed their own thesauri and vocabularies for FASTI for monument types (in English). AIAC hopes to map these to other thesauri such as the English Heritage Monument Type Thesaurus where appropriate.

NIAM-BAS uses a proprietary vocabulary in Bulgarian.

OEAW, ARHEO and **ATHENA RC – CETI** do not use any vocabularies or word lists.

5.3 Summary of datasets and collections

Partner Name	Content	Data Format	Number of Items
ADS	CAD, databases, GIS, images, video, spreadsheets, text, statistics, VR, geophysics, audio, survey	CAD (SVG, DXF), databases (delimited text), GIS (shape files), images (raster), video (MPG, AVI), spreadsheets (CSV), text (PDF/A), statistics (delimited text), VR/Video (MPG, AVI, MOV, FLV/WRL), geophysics/survey (DAT, DZT, GSI, raster), audio (MP3)	248,072 Image files (raster) 55,247 PDF 2,283 Text 2,616 CAD/Vector 9,324 XLS/CSV Spreadsheets 581 MPG/AVI/MOV/FLV/WRL VR/Video 70 MP3 Audio 150 DBF/MDB Databases 689 DAT/DZT/GSI Geophysics/Survey 936 SBN/PRJ/SBX/SHX/XYZTFW GIS 3145 HTML/CSS/XML
KNAW-DANS	Text documents, images (photos and scans), GIS, CAD, data tables	JPEG, MPEG, xml, text, binary, Quicktime, HTML, PDF/A, CSV, MID/MIF, DXF, SVG, and TIFF.	Over 1,561,838 data files in the archaeological section of EASY collection. These files consists of Over 17,000 reports Over 3,000 large datasets of text documents, images (photos and scans), GIS, CAD, data tables
DAI	Images and text	JPEG, TIFF and xml	1,7 million images registered; 700.000 book pages in about 3.650 books 220.000 objects and buildings and 20.000 topographies; 3.200.000 relations between ARACHNE records
ATHENA RC-CETI	Numerical data, text, images (pictures, diagrammes, plots)	Numerical data (ASCII), JPEG, PDF, proprietary binary file formats from scientific software packages	Approx. 1500 ceramic sherds
DISCOVERY	Text with some associated images, scientific reports and laboratory data, database records.	Online MySQL database, also contains associated jpeg images	Data of 21,000 stone axeheads, 3000 drawings/images, 500 petrographic thin section images.
SND	GIS data, text, databases	Pdf, mdb, shp (ESRI GIS)	361 pdf-files (reports), 386 shape-files (ESRI-GIS), 355 access data bases.
ZRC-SAZU	Text, images	html, mdb, jpg, gif	ca 3000items, ca 5500 images

Partner Name	Content	Data Format	Number of Items
MNK-NOK	Text, GIS files of archaeological sites and excavations, drawings and photos of finds	TIFF, JPEG, PDF, MDB, XLS, DOC, DWG, SHP, GPX	Reports and documentation of 1038 excavations Field survey reports and documentation of more than 3000 sites, geophysical survey reports of more than 50 sites Reports and documentation of more than 550 scientific analyses
CYI-STARC	2D Images and 3D Models	JPEG, PNG, 3D PDF, XML	2193 2D Images, 324 3D PDF
ARUP-CAS	Digital photographs; GIS information layers; database	JPEG; MDB; SHP	10,000 photographs; ca. 1,000 site entries film (description is under progress as part of the ARIADNE project)
OEAW	text with hyperlinks to the images, image and text	Mbd, TIFF	about 74.000 entries
AIAC	Text with metadata associated with site/intervention summaries, images, and links to online videos	JPG, PDF, HTML	5000+ site/season records 286 files
NIAM-BAS	Text, classification and characteristics defined over multiple nomenclatures, GPS location, images	Database (SQLite), JPG, PNG and GIF DOC and PDF formats	Around 17000.
MiBACT-ICCU	Text, image, 3D, GIS location. Scientific documentation survey reports; cartographic, graphic and photographic documentation; multimedia contents; 3D models	Pdf, doc, odt, jpg, tiff, xls, mdb, avi, mov, dwg, dxf, shp, obj, fbx, PostgreSQL RDBMS, Map Guide OS Library resources (xml files for layers and map objects definitions)	52.193 metadata with a preview image 11.000 geoDB SITAR records (OI, PA, UA, DT); 100.000 digital contents
ARHEO	maps, text descriptions of sites, database of alpha-numerical data, images.	xls, jpeg, dbase, Google maps	ca. 1,000
INRAP	Open data : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geolocation • Content database : excavations card index Open content associated: Each excavations card index summarizes the information and artifacts collected on the field and can be associated to photographs, short films or audio content. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Text • Documents • Photographs • Short videos (< 10 minutes) • Audio recordings 	Geolocation: National Coordinate Reference Systems Lambert 93 Content database: HTML Editorial content: PDF (documents) JPG, PNG (images) HTML (text) MOV, AVI, MP4 (movies) MP3 (audio) Dataset : excel	1 100 archaeological sites

Table 1: Datasets and collections

5.4 Summary of metadata schemas and vocabularies used by partners

Partner Name	Metadata Schema	Vocabularies
ADS	Proprietary The ADS Archive Metadata Schema is based on some of the metadata collected for each archive at the ADS. The schema is mostly aligned with the Collections Management System (CMS) used by the ADS to manage its archives.	Word List
KNAW-DANS	DCCD: The TRiDaS Standard (http://www.tridas.org/). EDNA: Qualified Dublin Core	DCCD: Multi lingual controlled vocabulary EDNA: the controlled vocabularies Archaeological Basis Register ABR
DAI	177 table of database MySQL Data can be harvested via OAI-PMH in the original format, Qualified Dublin Core, CIDOC-CRM and TEI	-GND (Gemeinsame Normdatei), http://www.dnb.de/DE/Standardisierung/GND/gnd_node.html , especially used for named entities of persons -Geonames, the DAI is in the process of restructuring its authority files and just recently established a new gazetteer, iDAI.gazetteer (http://gazetteer.dainst.org/)
ATHENA RC-CETI	Proprietary schema	N/A
DISCOVERY	Database records All web services have appropriate metadata which conforms to the EU INSPIRE directive and ISO 11915	-Geographic place names: based on Irish place-names database (logainm.ie) - Monument classification vocabularies based upon Irish National Monuments Service monument list - Artifact classification based upon National Museum of Ireland (NMI) list -Petrology based upon Irish Geological Survey classifications -Keywords use themes - GEMET v2.4 -Spatial Data Themes uses INSPIRE theme list
SND	DDI2.5, DDI3.1, DC, DC terms, DataCite, MARC-XML	-ELSST (European Language Social Science Thesaurus) -a local vocabulary which includes among other the monument type vocabularies of the Swedish National Heritage Board (RAÄ)
ZRC-SAZU	Proprietary	Proprietary
MNK-NOK	Schemes are available only for excavation dataset. Schemes contain: list of types, periods, material, condition and acquisition of objects.	Proprietary
CYI-STARC	-STARC metadata schema. -Customized LIDO metadata schema. -CyInscription metadata schema	N/A
ARUP-CAS	Proprietary	Standardized thesauri developed within the ARIADNE project
OEAW	Database records	N/A
AIAC	Proprietary – on going mapping to CIDOC CRM	Proprietary
NIAM-BAS	Proprietary	Proprietary

Partner Name	Metadata Schema	Vocabularies
MIBACT-ICCU	PICO Application profile SI– Archaeological Site SAS – Stratigraphical Probe MA/CA - Archaeological Monument / Archaeological Complex RA – Archaeological Find NU – Numismatics TMA –Archaeological Materials Report AT– Anthropological Finds	PICO Thesaurus Thesaurus for object definition Open vocabulary for class and production -Materials and technique vocabulary Vocabulary for object definition -SITAR vocabularies -ISTAT (Italian statistical agency) and Municipality of Rome and of Fiumicino vocabulary -Italian cadastral agency -Buildings Techniques
ARHEO	No metadata, data organized in databases and Google maps	N/A
INRAP	-DOLIA: The metadata schema is UNIMARC compliant -Archeozoom database: N/A -« description – fonds IDA » Iconothèque – Images d’Archéologie (IDA): N/A	-DOLIA: Four of the six Pactols thesauri from Frantiq network are used in Dolia : Places, People, Chronology and Subject. -Archeozoom database: N/A -« description – fonds IDA » Iconothèque – Images d’Archéologie (IDA): N/A

Table 2: Metadata schemas and vocabularies

6 Conclusions

ARIADNE plans to bring together and integrate diverse archaeological datasets so that researchers can make use of these resources and benefit from the technologies being made available as part of the research infrastructure.

During autumn 2013 a survey was carried out to gather information about the datasets that the partners plan to provide to ARIADNE for integration. Partners were asked to complete a questionnaire supplying information about their content its scope, format, size; the metadata available, the standards, schemas, and controlled vocabularies used; and also the rights and access framework. All partners who will provide content completed the survey.

The survey revealed that the consortium holds a very wide range of different types of dataset including:

- Archaeological databases: sites, settlements, burials finds, objects specific to particular regions and time periods
- Specialist object databases: stone axes, lithic tools
- Research datasets
- Ethno-archaeology datasets
- Archaeological science databases including wood, charcoal, palaeo-environmental fragments; c14 and isotope data; dendrochronology; archaeozoology; petrology, geophysical data, ceramic analysis; chemical analyses of ceramics and clays
- Archaeological excavations – sites, artefacts, reports
- Remote sensing datasets including lidar, aerial photography and geophysics
- Archaeological GIS: maps of archaeological sites, monuments, field investigations within regions, sites identified by aerial photography; GIS data including shape files
- Unpublished reports and other literature (so called ‘grey literature’)
- Photographic datasets; PDF and other text documents; Excel spreadsheets and CSV files; Movies; Audio files; and 3D models in a wide range of formats

Table 3 represents a preliminary attempt to seek areas of commonality within the wide range of datasets being made available via ARIADNE project partners. The aim of this preliminary analysis is to identify possible datasets where integration at item level could provide an invaluable resource for European researchers. This needs to be investigated further via the more detailed dataset metadata registry, but it is anticipated that it will lead to a fuller design and specification under Deliverables 12.1 and 13.1 in M15.

Divisions between categories of dataset are somewhat arbitrary at this stage, and are based upon partners’ initial brief summaries. Several datasets may also appear under several categories, and partners may also be able to identify areas where they have additional relevant data. However, the table already demonstrates some areas of critical mass where integration could be worthwhile.

Sites and monuments databases. Most European countries and regions hold inventories of known archaeological sites and monuments within their area. These are often developed for management purposes, but also provide an invaluable research resource. In addition several partners are also offering

datasets of sites of specific classes or periods. Although not comprehensive they could usefully be searched alongside the management-driven records. The inventories are generally characterised by fields for place, period and multiple keywords for site or monument type. Spatial data may be precise enough to support a GIS function. Given that most archaeological research questions are cross-border (e.g. “Where are all the Bronze Age sites in southern Europe?”) there is a value-added from combining inventories that ARIADNE is uniquely placed to provide.

Event/ intervention databases. This category of record is closely related to the previous grouping but provides instead a record of where archaeological fieldwork has been carried out, as opposed to where known sites are. In database terms there will frequently be a one-to-many relationship between monuments and events, as each site will have been subject to multiple investigations over time. It is the events, however, that provide most information about a site or monument. A special category of event databases held by several partners are effectively bibliographic metadata records for unpublished fieldwork reports, or ‘grey literature’. There is a widely recognized problem within Europe for researchers to gain access to this literature, which was highlighted in the description of work, and it has already been identified as a priority for online access and integration at European level. As the records share several fields with the sites and monuments inventories the network will need to decide if it wishes to combine both categories of data in a single search interface.

Fieldwork databases. Several partners have complete digital fieldwork archives available, including both excavation and geophysics data. Each archive may be a data collection, incorporating a range of file types with different record structures, and may range beyond simple text files to include GIS, databases, spreadsheets, images etc. In some cases the event databases (above) may provide an index record to the richer data collections. Given each collection will be site specific there will generally be little utility in integrating such datasets, although where WP16 is able to provide Linked Data at item level for finds records this may support research questions (e.g. “Where have Roman coins been deposited in later features?”)

The remaining categories reflect a wide variety of quite specific digital resources, but there may be some utility in integration, dependent upon the outcomes of the user needs studies.

Scientific databases may include, for example, environmental or faunal datasets, dating records, or the results of scientific analyses. Where such datasets are concerned the same analyses or data types they may share a relatively similar structure which will aid integration.

Databases of Artefacts provide access to information about specific objects at item level. Several partners have dedicated artifact databases, but they may also be present in fieldwork data collections. Some databases may include images of finds, or thumbnail links to separate image files. If there is a critical mass in specific categories of find, such as stone axes or ceramics for example, there could be considerable value added from providing transnational and cross-border interoperability.

Finally, **Burials** represent a special class of database where the individual grave represents the item level. The attributes recorded may include finds as well as physical anthropological information. Integration may aid studies of population demographics and social analyses. Cemeteries may also appear as single records in sites and monuments and events databases, which could provide a pointer to the richer item level datasets.

		Sites and monuments	Events/ Interventions	Fieldwork databases	Scientific	Artefacts	Burials
ZRC-SAZU	Slovenia	ZBIVA – 3000 early medieval sites in SE Alps					
OEAW	Austria	UK_Material-POOL – 442 LBA settlements		Thunau LBA and early med settlment			Franzhausen-Kokoron 3827 LBA graves
DISCOVERY	Ireland	NB Mapping Death – 174 early med cemeteries	SHARE-IT 50 site surveys		WODAN – wood and charcoal database for 533 sites	ISAP – 21000 Irish stone axes	Mapping Death – 174 early medieval cemeteries
ARHEO	Romania	BA and medieval sites survey		Geophysics data		Ceramics data	
INRAP	France		Arheozoom – 1100 excavation metadata records DOLIA – 500 pdf reports IDA – 3380 excavations				
ARUP-CAS	Czech Republic		AMCR – all field interventions in Bohemia				
NIAM-BAS	Bulgaria	Archaeological map – 17000 sites					
SND	Sweden		361 reports for Ostergotland	361 excavation archives			
ADS	UK	ArchSearch: 1,300,000 site records for archaeology of UK	25,000 grey literature reports	c.400 excavation archives	Dendrochronology; multiple environmental databases; grey lit reports	CBA Stone axe database for England & Wales; Ceramics	
DANS	Netherlands		17,000 grey literature reports	c.3000 datasets	DCCD – 50,000 records		

		Sites and monuments	Events/ Interventions	Fieldwork databases	Scientific	Artefacts	Burials
MiBACT-ICCU	Italy	SIGEC SITAR – UA dataset	SITAR – 11000 records	SITAR – PA dataset		Culturalitalia – 52000 objects	
MNM-NOK	Hungary		3000 sites; 1038 grey literature reports	geophysical survey of c. 50 sites	c. 550 reports	Ceramics, metal, glass, textile, human and animal bones, stone, archaeobotanical remains, other organic remains	
ATHENA RTC-CETI	Greece					Ceramics – 1500 sherds	
AIAC	Italy +		5000 excavations				
Cyi-STARC	Cyprus					2000+ images plus 300+3D models	
DAI	Germany					ARACHNE – 200,000+ classical archaeology artefacts	

Table 3 Datasets Categories

Given the varied and often specialist type of content that is being made available, there has been an equally varied range of approaches by partners to the adoption of standards for metadata and controlled vocabularies.

With regard to metadata standards, eight partners (SND, KNAW-DANS, Discovery, MiBACT-ICCU, INRAP, ADS, CYI-STARC) have adopted formal metadata standards for their datasets. The metadata standards adopted are: DDI, DataCite, MARC/UNIMARC, TriDAS, Dublin Core application profiles, INSPIRE, ISO 11915, CARARE, LIDO, CIDOC-CRM.

Ten partners (ZRC SAZU, MiBACT-ICCU, ADS, AIAC, OEAW, MNM-NOK, CYI-STARC, ARUP-CAS, ATHENA RC, NIAM-BAS) have developed proprietary metadata schemas for their datasets. While three partners (DISCOVERY, INRAP, ARHEO) reported datasets for which separate metadata is not currently available but could be derived from the content.

With regard to controlled vocabularies, only three partners reported using international standard vocabularies: SND, Discovery, INRAP. The vocabularies reported were: European Language Social Science Thesaurus, Irish place names database, Tree of Life project, Geological Survey of Ireland, GEMET, PACTOLS.

Four partners reported using national vocabularies: SND (monument type), KNAW-DANS (archaeology + ABR), Discovery (monument type and artifact classification), MiBACT-ICCU (PICO, SITAR vocabularies). While six partners reported using proprietary vocabularies developed specifically for their datasets (ZRC-SAZU, ADS, NUAM-BAS, AIC, MNM-NOK and Cyl-STARC). Three partners (OEAW, ARHEO and Athena RC-CETI) reported that they do not use vocabularies or wordlists.

The results of the survey of project partners datasets provides invaluable information which will inform the implementation of the project's metadata registry and will help the project to plan for ingestion. The datasets that have been identified provide the starting point. The project consortium anticipates that additional datasets will be identified during the lifetime of the project, through collaborations with archaeological organisations and projects on both national and international level.

The very wide range of content types that have been identified, their specialist nature and complexity confirms the need for ARIADNE to adopt a rich ontology to support their integration into the INFRASTRUCTURE. The CIDOC-CRM can provide such an ontology.

7 References

1. ADS: <http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/>
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8 Appendices

8.1 Appendix A / ADS

XML Properties

ID	PROPERTY	TYPE	DATA TYPE	OCCURANCES	DESCRIPTION
1	id	Property	Integer	1	The internal collection ID for the archive.
2	title	Property	String	1	The title of the archive.
3	description	Property	String	1	A description describing the archive.
4	version	Property	Integer	1	An integer which increases incrementally describing the version of the archive.
5	doi	Property	String	1	The DOI for the archive without the resolver, which for the ADS will have the prefix 10.5284/ .
6	type	Property	String	0...∞	A controlled list to describe the types of data within the archive. See list description below.
7	language	Property	String	1	The primary language of the data contained within the archive.
8.1	from	Property	Date	0...1	A date (year, year-month, or year-month-day) for the beginning of the data creation period.
8.2	to	Property	Date	0...1	A date (year, year-month, or year-month-day) for the end of the data creation period.
9.1	firstReleased	Property	Date	1	A date (year) for the original release of the data.
9.2	lastUpdated	Property	Date	0...1	A date (year) for the release of the most recent version of the data e.g. after an update.
10	actor	Property		1...∞	A property to describe an actor related to the archive.
10.1	[role]	Attribute	String	1	A controlled list to describe the role of the person or organisation. See list description below.
10.2	name	Property	String	0...1	The person's name related to the actor property. Each actor property must have at least a name or an organisation property to be valid.
10.3	[orcidId]	Attribute	String	0...1	The persons ORCID identifier.
10.4	organisation	Property	String	0...1	The organisation's name related to the actor property. Can be a standalone property or related to the name property of the actor.
10.5	email	Property	String	0...1	The email address of the person or organisation for the actor property.
11	subject	Property	String	1...∞	The subject keyword used to describe this archive.

ID	PROPERTY	TYPE	DATA TYPE	OCCURANCES	DESCRIPTION
11.1	[type]	Attribute	String	1	The thesauri or word list which the subject keyword is aligned with. See list description below.
12.1	country	Property		0...∞	A repeatable property to represent a country specific grid point related to the archive data.
12.2	[type]	Attribute	String	1	The coordinate system the easting and northing represent.
12.3	easting	Property	Number	1	The easting coordinate of the property.
12.4	northing	Property	Number	1	The northing coordinate of the property.
13.1	world	Property		0...∞	A repeatable property to represent the locational coordinates related to the archive data.
13.2	[type]	Attribute	String	1	The coordinate system used to represent the latitude and longitude.
13.3	latitude	Property	Number	1	The latitude of the property.
13.4	longitude	Property	Number	1	The longitude of the property.
14.1	northLatitude	Property	Number	0...1	The northern most latitude for the archive's bounding box.
14.2	eastLongitude	Property	Number	0...1	The eastern most longitude for the archive's bounding box.
14.3	southLatitude	Property	Number	0...1	The southern most latitude for the archive's bounding box.
14.4	westLongitude	Property	Number	0...1	The western most longitude for the archive's bounding box.
15	location	Property	String	0...∞	A locational name for the data within the archive.
15.1	[type]	Attribute	String	1	The thesauri or word list which the location place property is related to. Could also be a more specific term to describe the place name. See list description below.
16	period	Property	String	0...∞	A period term to describe the archive content.
16.1	[type]	Attribute	String	1	The thesauri or word list which the subject property is aligned with.
17	dateRange	Property		0...∞	A repeatable property to represent the historical date ranges which the archive data refers to, e.g. 100 BC - 100 AD.
17.1	startYear	Property	Integer	1	A positive or negative integer representing the start year of the archive data. Negative values represent BC years.
17.2	endYear	Property	Integer	1	A positive or negative integer representing the end year of the archive data. Negative values represent BC years.
18	id	Property	String	0...∞	An identifier that is related to the archive. This can sometimes be from the depositor or a larger project identifier.

ID	PROPERTY	TYPE	DATA TYPE	OCCURANCES	DESCRIPTION
18.1	[type]	Attribute	String	1	The type of identifier that the id property is related to.
19	relation	Property		0...∞	A repeatable property to encapsulate other relationships with other resources for the archive or its data, e.g. publication, other digital resource, website, etc.
19.1	[type]	Attribute	String	1	The type of relationship the relation property is representing. Usually a predicate (ie. Is Part Of).
19.2	title	Property	String	1	The main title or description of the relation property.
19.3	uri	Property	String	0...1	A URI for the relation property if it exists.
20	dissemination	Property		0...1	A property to encapsulate all of the dissemination digital objects.
20.1	category	Property		1...∞	A property to encapsulate a particular "category" of digital objects. The category relates to general groups of files (ie. Text, Raster Images, GIS, etc).
20.2	[type]	Attribute	String	1	The value of the category type. A word list below can be consulted or the catch-all value of "unknown" can be used.
21	fileType	Property		1...∞	A repeatable property to encapsulate a group of files based on the file extension.
21.1	extension	Property	String	1	The extension of the files related to the fileType property.
21.2	id	Property	String	0...∞	The PRONOM ID of the files with that file extension.
21.3	count	Property	Integer	0...1	The total number of files with this file extension.
21.4	size	Property	Number	0...1	The total size in Megabytes for files with this file extension.
22	repository	Property	String	1	The name of the repository responsible for the preservation of this data.
23	licence	Property	String	1	A description of the licence or reuse conditions associated with the data.
23.1	type	Attribute	String	1	A controlled list of values to define the type of licence associated with the data.
24	fileIdentifier	Property	String	1	A UUID to uniquely identify the whole metadata record. This UUID can be used to confirm that metadata has not changed.

Word Lists

ID 6: type

NAME	DESCRIPTION
Dataset Collection	An archive containing mixed data types
Image Collection	An archive containing but not limited to images
Interactive Resource Collection	An archive containing but not limited to interactive content. This could include HTML pages or bespoke interfaces not developed by the ADS
Moving Image Collection	An archive containing but not limited to moving images such as movies or animated GIFs
Software Collection	An archive containing but not limited to software or executable code
Sound Collection	An archive containing but not limited to audio files
Text Collection	An archive containing but not limited to textual data, such as reports or scanned journals

ID 10.1: role

NAME	DESCRIPTION
funder	The funder of the project
creator	The creator of the project

ID 11.1: type

NAME	DESCRIPTION
General Subject	A general subject description used within the ADS interface
LCSH	Library of Congress Subject Heading
MDA Archaeological Objects	
MEDIN Category	
NMR Archaeological Sciences	
NMR Building Materials	
NMR Components	
NMR Defence of Britain	
NMR Event Types	
NMR Evidence	
NMR Historic Aircraft Types	
NMR Maritime Craft Types	
NMR Monument Types	
NMR Monument Types (class)	
RCAHMS Maritime	
Thred Thesaurus	
None	No Thesauri or word list associated with this term

ID 15.1: type

NAME	DESCRIPTION
British Isles Country	
Community	
County	
District	
Historic Place	
Non British Isles Country	
Parish	
Place	Used for places both inside the British Isles and elsewhere
TGN	Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names
Townland	
None	No Thesauri or word list associated with this term

ID 16.1: type

NAME	DESCRIPTION
MIDAS	
None	No Thesauri or word list associated with this term

ID 20.2: type

NAME	DESCRIPTION
Audio	
Database	
Geophysics	
GIS	
Movies	
Raster Image	
Spreadsheet	
Text	
Vector Graphics	
Virtual Reality	
Unknown	Other data category or unknown

ID 23.1: type

NAME	DESCRIPTION
cc by	Creative Commons Attribution
cc by-sa	Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike
cc by-nc	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial
other	A different licence than Creative Commons, which must be partially described in the licence property

8.2 Appendix B / ZRC-SAZU

ARKAS database (proprietary metadata schema)

Field names and description (Slovenian and English in alphabetical order)

Original name	Translation (field name)	Description
ANSL	ANSI	ANSI (= Arheološka najdišča Slovenije, 1975)
AtlasSLO	Atlas of Slovenia	Atlas of Slovenia (1:50,000)
Dat_izkop	Date of excavation	Date of excavation
Dat_konz	Date of conservation	Date of conservation
Dat_nadzor	Date of arch. control	Date of arch. control
Dat_obhoda	Date of surveillance	Date of surveillance
Dat_Omembe	Date of first mention	Date of first mention
Dat_vnosa	Date of input	Date of entry
Datacija	Period	Archaeological period (see the table below)
Hramba	Keeping	Finds kept in/at
ID_datacije	ID_period	ID_period
ID_izkopa	ID_excavat	ID_excavation
ID_Karta25	ID_map25	ID_map25
ID_Karta5	ID_map5	ID_map5
ID_konz	ID_conservation	ID_conservation
ID_Nadzor	ID_control	ID_control
ID_najdbe	ID_find	ID_find
ID_najdisca	ID_site	ID_site
ID_naselja	ID_place	ID_place
ID_obhoda	ID_surveillance	ID_surveillance
ID_osebe	ID_person	ID_person
ID_raba	ID_use	ID_use
ID_stanja	ID_state	ID_state
ID_TE	ID_TE	ID_TE
ID_TP	ID_TP	ID_TP
Ime	Name	Name of the site (street name, plot or field name, etc.)
Ime_osebe	Name of the person	Name of the person(s) excavated, surveyed etc. the site
Izkopavanja	Excavations	Excavations (year(s))
Karta25	Map25 (= 1:25,000)	Map1:25,000
Karta5	Map5 (=1:5,000)	Map 1:5,000
Konzervacija	Conservation	Conservation
KoordX	CoordX	Coord. X (Gauß-Krüger coordinate system)
KoordY	CoordY	Coord. Y (Gauß-Krüger coordinate system)
Lastnik	Owner	Owner (of the plot, field, house)
NadMVis	Above sea level	Above sea level
Nadzor	Control	Archaeol. control
Najdba	Find	Site type/ category -- levels 1, 2 and 3 -- see the table below
Najdišče	Site	Site
Naselje	Place (= town, village etc)	Place (= town, village etc.)
Omemba	Mention	First mention in bibl.

Original name	Translation (field name)	Description
Opis	Description	Description of the site
Opredelitev	Definition	Definition (chronol.)
Ostalalit	Other bibl.	Other bibl.
Obhodi	Surveillance	Surveillance (year(s))
Ohranjenost	Preservation	Preservation
Oseba	Person	Person(s) excavated, surveyed etc. the site
Parcela	Plot	Plot (no. and name of the administrative unit)
Pri_osebe	Surname of person	Surname of person(s) excavated, surveyed etc. the site
Raba	Usage	Usage of the land
Stanje	State	State of preservation of the site
TE	TE (= topographical unit)	TE (= topographical unit)
TP	TP (= topographical area)	TP (= topographical area)
Vir	Source	Source
Vnesel	Entry by	Entry by
Zaselek	Other name	Other name(s) of the site

Period description

ID_dating	sequence	Archaeological period	From	To
PL	0	Pleistocene		
P	1	Paleolithic	1,500,000 BP	10,000 BP
STP	2	Lower Palaeolithic	1,500,000 BP	130,000 BP
SRP	3	Middle Palaeolithic	130,000 BP	35,000 BP
MLP	4	Upper Palaeolithic	35,000 BP	10,000 BP
M	5	Mezolithic	8000 BC	5000 BC
PR	6	Prehistory	1,500,000 BP	30 BC
N	7	Neolithic	5000 BC	2800 BC
STN	8	Early Neolithic	5000 BC	4000 BC
SRN	9	Middle Neolithic	4000 BC	3500 BC
MLN	10	Late Neolithic	3500 BC	2800 BC
BD	11	Copper Age	2800 BC	1800/1750 BC
ZBA	12	Early Copper Age	2800 BC	2500 BC
SBA	13	Middle Copper Age	2500 BC	2200 BC
PBA	14	Late Copper Age	2200 BC	1800/1750 BC
BRD	15	Bronze Age	1750 BC	750 BC
STB	16	Early Bronze Age	1750 BC	1500 BC
SRB	17	Middle Bronze Age	1500 BC	1250 BC
MLB	18	Late Bronze Age	1250 BC	1000 BC
PZB	19	Urnfield period	1000 BC	750 BC
ZD	20	Iron Age	750 BC	30 BC
STZ	21	Early Iron Age	750 BC	300 BC
MLZ	22	Late Iron Age	300 BC	30 BC
RD	23	Roman period	30 BC	600 AD
ZRD	24	Early Roman period	30 BC	300 AD
PRD	25	Late Antiquity	300 AD	600 AD
SV	26	Middle Ages	600 AD	1500 AD
ZG	27	Early Middle Ages	600 AD	1000 AD
VI	28	High Middle Ages	1000 AD	1300 AD

ID_dating	sequence	Archaeological period	From	To
POZ	29	Late Middle Ages	1300 AD	1500 AD
NO	30	Post-Middle Ages	1500 AD	
NE	31	undefined		

Find Classification

Level	Classification
1	cave site
1	upland site
1	lowland site
1	under-water site
2	residence (in the cave)
2	hoard
2	(undefined) structure(s)
2	cemetery
2	settlement
2	isolated find
3	pile-dwelling
3	lime kiln
3	road
3	church
3	boat
3	workshop
3	logboat
3	other
3	mansion
3	frescoes
3	tumulus (unidentified)
3	tumuli/barrow cemetery
3	castle
3	hypocaust
3	house
3	ingot
3	ditch
3	sewage
3	bath/thermae
3	baptistery
3	cult place
3	hearth
3	pottery
3	milestone
3	bridge
3	mosaic
3	gravestone
3	jewellery
3	inscription stone

Level	Classification
3	embankment
3	undefined architectural remains
3	unfortified settlement
3	coin
3	walls
3	flake
3	fireplace
3	constraint
3	altar
3	human bones and teeth
3	plant remains (wood)
3	animal remains (bones, teeth, hair)
3	tools
3	weapons
3	furnace
3	cinerary urn
3	flat cemetery
3	vessels
3	port
3	monastery
3	sarcophagus
3	warehouse
3	sculpture
3	tower
3	raw material
3	sanctuary
3	camp
3	market/forum
3	smelter
3	fort
3	fortified settlement
3	villa
3	cistern
3	plumbing
3	claustra (defence wall)
3	land distribution
3	urn
3	stone altar
3	slag
3	grave
3	horseshoe
3	raw (unworked) stone
3	oil lamp
3	mine
3	brick
3	quarry

Level	Classification
3	relief
3	channel
3	tomb
3	well
3	mould
3	candlestick
3	horse gear (riding equipment)

Zbiva: Description of fields

name	description
ID	ID
Code	Code of the site (link to Code in table Bridge)
Name	Field name, name of the site, street name etc.
Other_name	Other name(s), nearest hamlet
Settlement	Modern name
Topograph_unit	Topographical unit (administrative)
Topograph_area	Topographical area (administrative)
Region	Region (for Austria, Italy and Croatia)
Country	Country
Finds_old	Old (= longer) description of the site and finds
Finds	castle, church, church, graveyard church, graveyard, monastery church, fortification church, monastery fortification fortification, graveyard graveyard monastery pit road, path sanctuary separate find (isolated find) settlement settlement, church settlement, church, graveyard settlement, graveyard story, narrative (folk) undefined workshop
Period	Archaeological period
From	From year
To	To year
Cultural	Slavic, Avarian, Merovingian etc.
Notes	Notes on the site, dating, cultural interpretation etc.
Kept_in	Find are kept in ...
Usage_land	Usage of the land (parcel no., filed, wood etc.)

name	description
Area	Area: descriptive (e.g. SE of the village; 700 m E from the railway station etc.)
First_mentioned	ID of the publication with the site first mentioned
Year	Year of the first mentioning
Sources_description	Description of the source of the first mention (surveillance, by mouth, visiting excavation etc.)
Excavated_by	Name of the excavator(s) -- if known
Excav_year	Year(s) of the excavation

Libera: Description of fields

name	description
ID_Libera	ID (link to ID_Libere in table Bridge)
Author	Author(s)
Caption	Caption
Publ_series	Publication, series, review
Place_of_publ	Publishing place
Year_of_publ	Publishing year
Pages	Pages of the article

Bridge: Description of fields

name	description
ID_Libera	ID of bibl. (link to table Libera)
Code	Code of the site (link to table Zbiva)
Citation	Exact page, figures etc.

8.3 Appendix C / NIAM-BAS

The list below includes most important fields and nomenclatures used in AKB (AMB) and omits or includes brief description of less important or not actively used ones. They describe the main entity of the data set – archaeological object/site.

Field name (or field group)	Field type	Description
SID	INTEGER	Internal identifier for the database – same value for all languages.
Security descriptor fields	Security and ownership descriptor	Group of fields containing ownership, access rights, creation and modification times and other record level access control information.
LOCATION_SID	NOMENCLATURE	Locations nomenclature contains the modern settlements and administrative divisions of Bulgaria. Typically the attribute points to the closest settlement or at least a county/district for ambiguous locations. Tree hierarchy with supporting linear nomenclature describing the type of element (<i>the nomenclature is not listed in this document</i>)
OWNERSHIP_SID	NOMENCLATURE	Linear nomenclature – describes the modern time ownership of the terrain (or the primary form of property ownership in some cases).
TERRAINUSAGE_SID	NOMENCLATURE	Linear nomenclature. Modern usage of the terrain of the site.
GEOFORM_SID	NOMENCLATURE	
OROGRAPHY_SID	NOMENCLATURE	Hierarchical nomenclature – orography system to which the site/object belongs. <i>The nomenclature is not listed in this document.</i>
HYDROGRAPHY_SID	NOMENCLATURE	Hierarchical nomenclature. Specifies the river basin in which the site resides (entered with varied precision). <i>The nomenclature is not listed in this document.</i>
SOIL_TYPES_SID	NOMENCLATURE	Hierarchical nomenclature. Primary soil type – varied precision. <i>The nomenclature is not listed in this document.</i>
ACCESSIBILITY_SID	NOMENCLATURE	Linear nomenclature. Describes in a few simple categories how accessible the site is.
OBSERVABILITY_SID	NOMENCLATURE	Linear nomenclature. Describes the visibility of the site.
SLOPE_SID	NOMENCLATURE	Linear nomenclature. Rough characterization of the slope for the sites where this is applicable.
CONCENTRATION_SID	NOMENCLATURE	Linear nomenclature. Simple categorization of the distribution of the findings (tools, vessels etc.). The usefulness is probably controversial, however the categorization is general enough to give a hint, but not force the user to fill in incorrect or too specific characterization data.

Field name (or field group)	Field type	Description
GROUPING_SID	NOMENCLATURE	Linear nomenclature. Similar to the concentration, but characterizes the grouping – the same considerations apply.
Legal status, protection and importance.	A group of nomenclatures	A number of simple linear nomenclatures describing roughly characteristics such as legal status, protection type, conservation efforts and so on. Part of the data may be useful for inter-system exchange. Part of the data describes characteristics that change through time and its precision will vary depending on the time from the last confirmation/change. <i>The nomenclatures are not listed in this document.</i>
PLACE_ADDRESS	TEXT	Address of the site (or the closest settlement/landmark). This field is free text in Bulgarian.
RELATIVE_LOCALIZATION	TEXT	Free text description of the location of the site relative to the closest settlement. This field is in Bulgarian and often contains local names of landmarks.
ELEVATION	INTEGER	Elevation over the sea level (min and max xor average in meters).
ARCHIVE_INFO	TEXT	Free text in Bulgarian. References to archive, museum and other sources of information related to the site/object.
MUSEUM_INFO	TEXT	
OTHER_INFO	TEXT	
RESEARCH_HISTORY	TEXT	Free text in Bulgarian describing known previous research of the object/site.
AREA	NUMERIC	Surface area in decars (where applicable).
SPECIFICS	TEXT	Specifics of the site/object not belonging to other fields (free text in Bulgarian).
Localization map and plot.	Image (png), date, scale, author	Scanned, exported (from various 3-d party software) images of plot and localization map (if applicable) of the site/object. Maintained from 2009, older entries do not include images. The scale of the plot, the map and the author are also recorded into the database.
BELONG_COMPLEX	TEXT	If known and fairly probable the name of the complex to which the site/object belongs (Rarely filled). Text in Bulgarian.
BELONG_SYSTEM	TEXT	If known and fairly probable the name of the system of sites to which the site/object belongs (Rarely filled). Text in Bulgarian.
BELONG_CULTURE	TEXT	If known and fairly probable the culture to which the site/object belongs. Text in Bulgarian.
COMMENTS	TEXT	General comments of any kind. Text in Bulgarian.

Field name (or field group)	Field type	Description
CREATOR_PERSON_SID***	LINK TO PERSONS	Link to the registered person who is responsible for the entry creation and maintenance.
CHECKED_PERSON_SID***	LINK TO PERSONS	Link to the registered person who verified the entry.
CREATED_DATE	DATETIME	Date of creation - manually set when the entry is finished, an automatic record of the creation date also exists, but it is of interest only for the system administration.
OBJECT_NUMBER	TEXT	Local object identification number. Legacy field and currently filled with a number determined by the organization that works on the site. Usually refers to local non-electronic documentation.
CARD_NUMBER	TEXT	Unique entry identifier with more human manageable size than the internal database id.
COMPLETED	BOOLEAN	Is the entry completed or still worked on.
LATITUDE	DOUBLE	GPS coordinates of the site/object. Filled after 2009, some old entries have been amended, but not all.
LONGITUDE	DOUBLE	
STATUS_SID*	NOMENCLATURE	Link to a nomenclature with several entries for the possible status of the site/object. This is only the status for the last report and a log of the observed and reported states of the site/object is kept in order to track violations, damages caused by natural disasters and so on. <i>The nomenclature is not listed in this document.</i>
STATUS_COMMENTS	TEXT	Go together with the status above – a link to the person who reported it and free text description (if needed).
STATUS_PERSON_SID	INTEGER	
PUBLICATIONS_INFO	TEXT	Free text in Bulgarian with publications about the site/object.
OBJECT_NAME	TEXT	Free text – name of the object. This field exists from 2009, older entries have only OBJECT_NUMBER, a few are amended.
OBJECT_DESCRIPTION	TEXT	Optional free text description of the site/object intended for professionals and semi-professionals and more public use in future. Rarely filled.
GPS_NOTPRECISE	BOOLEAN	Indications for non-precise GPS coordinates (usually taken from the map and not measured at the site).
Multiple FINDINGS**	NOMENCLATURE	Multiple entries describing the kind of objects/tools found (only the most important ones).
Multiple FACILITIES**	NOMENCLATURE	Multiple entries describing the kind of facilities found.

Field name (or field group)	Field type	Description
Multiple combined pairs TYPE_AND_PERIOD**	NOMENCLATURES	Using two nomenclatures (listed further in the document) this describes the type and historical period of the most important findings/facilities/roles of the site/object. As an example one can specify church-early medieval. This was and is the most stressed part of the entry data and at least the most notable characteristics/findings are described this way. Additional (up to 512 characters) short description can be attached to each entry.
Photos and other images	Up to 20 images with captions	Link to mostly JPEG (PNG and GIF are also allowed) images related to the entry. What is included depends on the specifics of the site/object and may vary from photos of the site to photos of artifacts found.
Documents	Up to 20 documents limited to 2MB each.	Optional additional documents that can be attached to the entry – mostly DOC and PDF. This is a new feature and exists from 2010, may contain useful information mostly for researchers who will continue the work on site and rarely has any value for the public.

* - The status is required every time the entry is changed, so a new one is recorded when the data is amended. This policy was introduced lately in an effort to keep some track of the state of the sites/objects in parallel with the other work the users of the system do.

** - Although the findings and facilities usually correspond to type-period characteristics, this is not a must. The reasons can vary from lack of enough information about some of them to the focus of the research on certain period or the inclination of the user.

*** - Persons responsible for entries or creation of plots, maps, or verification of entries are kept as unique “person” entries in the database and relations to them are established.

Nomenclatures: The tables below list the nomenclatures most usable for intersystem data exchange and conversion to other metadata standards. The terms are in Bulgarian language. We are in the process of translating them in English.

TYPE (hierarchical)

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
0	ВОДОСНАБДЯВАНЕ И КАНАЛИЗАЦИЯ	-
1	->БАРАЖИ, БЕНТОВЕ	-
1	->ВОДОПРОВОДИ	-
2	->->Акведукти	-
1	->ВОДОХРАНИЛИЩА /ЩЕРНИ/	-
1	->КАНАЛИ	-
1	->КАПТАЖИ	-
1	->КЛАДЕНЦИ	-
0	ДРУГИ ОБЕКТИ	-
1	->ИЗОЛИРАНА СЛЕДА ОТ ДЕЙНОСТТА НА ЧОВЕКА	-

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
1	->ОБЕКТ С НЕОПРЕДЕЛЕНА ФУНКЦИЯ	-
1	->СЛЕДИ ОТ СТАРИ НИВИ	-
1	->СЪКРОВИЩЕ	-
2	->->Монетно	-
2	->->От глинени съдове	-
2	->->От оръдия на труда	-
2	->->От предмети от благородни метали	-
0	КУЛТОВИ СЪОРЪЖЕНИЯ	-
1	->ДРУГИ КУЛТОВИ МЕСТА	-
1	->КУЛТОВИ КОМПЛЕКСИ	-
2	->->Манастир	-
1	->КУЛТОВИ ПОСТРОЙКИ	-
2	->->Други /джамия, синагога и др./	-
2	->->Параклис	-
2	->->Храм	-
2	->->Църква, базилика	-
1	->КУЛТОВИ ЯМИ	-
1	->МЕГАЛИТИ	-
2	->->Изсичания в скали	-
2	->->Менхири, побити камъни	-
2	->->Скален манастир	-
2	->->Скална църква	-
2	->->Скални ниши	-
2	->->Скално помещение	-
1	->СВЕТИЛИЩЕ	-
2	->->В пещера	-
2	->->Край извор	-
2	->->На връх	-
2	->->Скално	-
0	МЯСТО НА СРАЖЕНИЕ	-
0	ПОГРЕБАЛНИ ПРАКТИКИ	-
1	->ГРОБНИ СЪОРЪЖЕНИЯ	-
2	->->Градени	-

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
3	->->градеж на яма	-
3	->->гробници	-
3	->->долмени	-
3	->->скална гробница	-
2	->->Каменни кръгове	-
2	->->Ограждане с плочи или керемиди	-
2	->->Покриване и ограждане с ломени или речни камъни, керемиди	-
2	->->Саркофази	-
2	->->Яма	-
1	->ДРУГИ СЛЕДИ ОТ ПОГРЕБАЛНИ ПРАКТИКИ	-
1	->ЕДИНИЧНИ ГРОБОВЕ	-
1	->НАДГРОБНИ ПАМЕТНИЦИ	-
1	->НАЧИН НА ПОГРЕБВАНЕ	-
2	->->Кенотафи	-
2	->->Препогребване	-
2	->->Трупозгаряне	-
2	->->Трупопологане	-
2	->->Частични гробове	-
1	->НЕКРОПОЛИ	-
2	->->Могилни	-
3	->->вторични гробове в могилния насип	-
3	->->гробове или други съоръжения в краймогилното пространство	-
3	->->група могили	-
3	->->единична могила	-
2	->->Плоски	-
3	->->в границите на населено място	-
3	->->извън населено място	-
3	->->около и в култова постройка	-
2	->->Скални	-
2	->->Смесени	-
3	->->могилен с плоски гробове	-
3	->->плосък с могили	-

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
0	ПОДВОДНИ ОБЕКТИ	-
1	->ВЪЛНОЛОМ	-
1	->КОРАБ	-
1	->ОТДЕЛНИ ПРЕДМЕТИ	-
2	->->Амфора	-
2	->->Груп котви	-
2	->->Група амфори	-
2	->->Други	-
2	->->Котва	-
1	->ПРИСТАНИЩЕ	-
1	->СЕЛИЩЕ	-
0	ПРОИЗВОДСВЕНИ ЦЕНТРОВЕ И РАБОТИЛНИЦИ	-
1	->ДРУГИ РАБОТИЛНИЦИ	-
1	->КАМЕНОДЕЛНИ РАБОТИЛНИЦИ	-
1	->КЕРАМИЧНИ ПРОИЗВОДСВЕНИ ЦЕНТРОВЕ	-
2	->->Керамични пещи	-
2	->->Керамични работилници	-
2	->->Коропластни работилници	-
1	->МЕТАЛУРГИЯ	-
2	->->Бронзолеярски пещи	-
2	->->Бронзолеярски работилници	-
2	->->Желязодобивни пещи	-
2	->->Златарски работилници	-
2	->->Ковачници	-
1	->РАБОТИЛНИЦИ ЗА КОСТИ И РОГ	-
1	->СТЪКЛАРСКИ РАБОТИЛНИЦИ	-
1	->СЪОРЪЖЕНИЯ ЗА ОБРАБОТКА НА ХРАНИ	-
2	->->Винарски съоръжения	-
2	->->Мелници	-
0	ПЪТНИ СЪОРЪЖЕНИЯ	-
1	->БРОД	-
1	->МИЛИАРНИ КОЛОНИ	-
1	->МИТНИЦА	-

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
1	->МОСТ	-
1	->ПЪТ	-
1	->ПЪТНА СТАНЦИЯ	-
1	->СТЪЛБИЦА	-
1	->ТУНЕЛИ,ЗАСВОДЕНИ ПРОХОДИ	-
0	РАЗРАБОТКА НА ПРИРОДНИ СУРОВИНИ	-
1	->ДОБИВ НА ДРУГИ ПРИРОДНИ СУРОВИНИ	-
2	->->Други	-
2	->->Каменоломни	-
2	->->На глина	-
2	->->На дървени въглища	-
2	->->На пясък	-
1	->ДОБИВ НА КРЕМЪК, КВАРЦ	-
1	->ДОБИВ НА СОЛ	-
2	->->Рудници	-
2	->->Солници	-
1	->РУДОДОБИВ	-
2	->->Благородни метали	-
3	->->->минни разработки	-
3	->->->промиване	-
2	->->Желязна руда	-
3	->->->минни разработки	-
3	->->->повърхностна	-
2	->->Цветни метали	-
0	СЕЛИЩА И ГРАЖДАНСКИ ПОСТРОЙКИ	-
1	->ЕДИНИЧНА ПОСТРОЙКА	-
2	->->БАНЯ	-
1	->СЕЛА	-
2	->->С площ до 5 дка /махала/	-
2	->->С площ над 5 дка /коме,пагус и др./	-
2	->->Сезонно селище	-
1	->СЕЛИЩА ОТ ГРАДСКИ ТИП	-
2	->->Град	-

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
1	->СЕЛИЩА С КОНКРЕТНА ФУНКЦИЯ	-
2	->->Емпориум / тържище	-
2	->->Курортно селище	-
2	->->Седалище на владетел	-
2	->->Селско имение, вила рустика	-
1	->СЕЛИЩА С ОСОБЕНА ЛОКАЛИЗАЦИЯ	-
2	->->Наколно селище	-
2	->->Селище в пещера	-
2	->->Селищна могила	-
0	УКРЕПЕНИ МЕСТА И УКРЕПИТЕЛНИ СЪОРЪЖЕНИЯ	-
1	->ВОЕННИ ЛАГЕРИ	-
2	->->Аули	-
2	->->Кастели	-
1	->КРЕПОСТИ	-
2	->->Крепости - убежища	-
2	->->С укрепен квартал	-
1	->СТРАЖНИЦИ	-
1	->УКРЕПЕНИ КЪЩИ	-
1	->УКРЕПИТЕЛНИ СЪОРЪЖЕНИЯ	-
2	->->Валове	-
2	->->Каменни стени	-
2	->->Прокопи в скалите	-
2	->->Ровове	-
0	ХУДОЖЕСТВЕНИ И ДРУГИ ПАМЕТНИЦИ	-
1	->АРХИТЕКТУРНИ ЕЛЕМЕНТИ	-
1	->ГРАФИТИ	-
1	->МОЗАЙКИ	-
1	->НАДПИСИ	-
1	->ОБРОЧНИ ПЛОЧКИ	-
1	->РЕЛЕФИ	-
1	->СКАЛНИ РИСУНКИ	-
1	->СКУЛПТУРИ	-

CHRONOLOGY (hierarchical)

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
0	Исторически период	-
1	->Античност	-
1	->Възраждане	-
1	->Късна античност	-
1	->Късно желязна епоха	-
2	->>Елинистическа епоха	-
2	->>КЖЕ - втори период	-
2	->>КЖЕ - първи период	-
2	->>Класическа епоха	-
1	->Римска епоха	-
2	->>Късноримска епоха	-
2	->>Ранноримска епоха	-
1	->Средновековие	-
2	->>Византийско владичество	-
2	->>Втора българска държава	-
2	->>Късно средновековие	-
2	->>Първа българска държава	-
2	->>Раннославянски период	-
0	Неопределима	-
0	Праистория	-
1	->Бронзова епоха	-
2	->>Късна бронзова епоха	-
2	->>Ранна бронзова епоха	-
2	->>Средна бронзова епоха	-
1	->Енеолит	-
2	->>Късен енеолит	-
2	->>Ранен енеолит	-
2	->>Среден енеолит	-
1	->Желязна епоха	-
2	->>РЖЕ - втори период	-
2	->>РЖЕ - първи период	-
2	->>Ранножелязна епоха	-

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
2	->->Тракийски период	-
1	->Неолит	-
2	->->Късен неолит	-
2	->->Ранен неолит	-
2	->->Среден неолит	-
1	->Палеолит	-
2	->->Късен палеолит	-
2	->->Среден палеолит	-
1	->Преходен период	-

FACILITY (hierarchical)

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
0	Дървени	-
1	->ковчези	-
1	->останки от дървени конструкции	-
1	->палисади	-
0	Землени	-
1	->валове	-
1	->замазки	-
1	->зид от кирпич	-
1	->зид от тухли	-
1	->каналы (отводнителни съоръжения)	-
1	->мазилки	-
1	->могили	-
1	->огнища	-
1	->пещи	-
1	->ровове	-
1	->ями	-
0	Каменни	-
1	->архитектурни детайли	-
1	->водопроводи	-
1	->гробни съоръжения	-
1	->каналы	-
1	->кейове	-

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
1	->кръгове	-
1	->кръстове	-
1	->мостове	-
1	->настилки	-
1	->ниши	-
1	->олтари	-
1	->пещи	-
1	->площадки	-
1	->саркофази	-
1	->скални релефи	-
1	->стели	-
1	->стени	-
1	->струпвания	-
1	->стълбове	-
1	->стъпала	-
1	->хоросанови мазилки	-
1	->цисти	-
1	->шарапташи	-

FINDINGS (hierarchical)

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
0	Други	-
0	Дървени	-
1	->други	-
1	->дръжки	-
1	->икони и елементи от иконостаси	-
1	->инструменти	-
1	->лодки и плавателни съоръжения	-
1	->рабоши	-
1	->съдове	-
0	Каменни	-
1	->архитектурни детайли	-
1	->бойни топки	-
1	->други	-

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
1	->дялани камъни	-
1	->жертвеници	-
1	->калъпи и матирци	-
1	->каменни надписи	-
1	->купели	-
1	->ломени камъни	-
1	->мозаечни кубчета и инкрустации	-
1	->оръдия на труда	-
1	->оръжия	-
1	->предмети на култа	-
1	->релефи и оброчни плочи	-
1	->статуи	-
1	->съдове	-
1	->тежести	-
1	->хлебчета	-
1	->хромели	-
1	->щемпели	-
0	Керамични	-
1	->водопроводни тръби	-
1	->дискове	-
1	->други	-
1	->зарчета	-
1	->калъпи и матрици	-
1	->керемиди	-
1	->култови предмети	-
1	->късове замазка	-
1	->късове мазилка	-
1	->лампи	-
1	->мъниста	-
1	->печати	-
1	->прешлени	-
1	->статуетки и скулптурни изображения	-
1	->съдове	-
1	->тежести	-
1	->теракоти	-
1	->тухли	-

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
0	Кожени	-
1	->други	-
1	->обувки	-
1	->подвързии на книги	-
1	->ремъци	-
1	->части от облекло и въоръжение	-
0	Костени	-
1	->амулети	-
1	->други	-
1	->елементи от украса	-
1	->животински кости	-
1	->зарчета и пулове	-
1	->накити	-
1	->обкови	-
1	->оръдия на труда	-
1	->полуфабрикати	-
1	->прешлени	-
1	->раковини и миди със следи от обработка	-
1	->стилоси	-
1	->фигурки	-
1	->човешки кости	-
0	Кремъчни	-
1	->други	-
1	->кремъчна конкреция със следи от	-
1	->отломък без вторична обработка	-
1	->типологическо оръдие	-
1	->ядро	-
0	Метални	-
1	->апликации	-
1	->водопроводни тръби	-
1	->воинско снаряжение	-
1	->други	-
1	->конско снаряжение	-
1	->крици	-
1	->медальони	-
1	->медицински инструменти	-

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
1	->монети	-
1	->накити	-
1	->обкови	-
1	->огледала	-
1	->оръдия на труда	-
1	->оръжия	-
1	->печати	-
1	->пломби	-
1	->предмети с неясно предназначение	-
1	->светилници	-
1	->слитьци	-
1	->статуи и статуетки	-
1	->стилоси	-
1	->съдове	-
1	->тежести	-
1	->тоалетни принадлежности	-
1	->шлака	-
0	Предмети от благородни и полубл. камъни	-
1	->геми	-
1	->други	-
1	->камеи	-
1	->полуфабрикати	-
1	->части от накити	-
0	Стъклени	-
1	->детайли от други предмети	-
1	->други	-
1	->инкрустации и мозаечни кубчета	-
1	->накити	-
1	->полуфабрикати и производствени	-
1	->прозрачно стъкло	-
1	->съдове	-
0	Текстилни	-
1	->тъкани	-

GEOFORM (hierarchical)

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
0	Брегова ивица	-
0	Валог (ерозионен валог)	-
0	Вододел	-
0	Възвишение (хълм)	-
1	->Връх на възвишение	-
1	->Подножие на възвишението	-
1	->Склон на възвишение	-
2	->->Горна част на склона	-
2	->->Долна част на склона	-
2	->->Средна част на склона	-
0	Делта	-
0	Дол	-
0	Ждрело	-
0	Залив	-
0	Заравнена повърхнина (денудационна равнина)	-
0	Кално-каменен поток	-
0	Карстово поле (карово поле)	-
1	->Кари	-
0	Котловина	-
0	Крайбрежие	-
0	Крайбрежни дюни	-
0	Лагуна	-
0	Лиман	-
0	Меандър	-
0	Наносен конус	-
0	Неопределена	-
0	Нос	-
0	Овраг (дере)	-
0	Остров	-
0	Падина	-
0	Пещера	-

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
1	->Пещерни галерии	-
1	->Пещерни зали	-
1	->Пещерно преддверие	-
0	Пещера крепост (карстов кладенец)	-
0	Плаж	-
0	Полуостров	-
0	Провлак	-
0	Речен остров	-
0	Речна долина	-
1	->Долинен склон	-
1	->Долинно дъно	-
2	->->Пойма (саливна речна тераса)	-
2	->->Русло	-
1	->Език на речната тераса	-
1	->Речен бряг	-
1	->Речна тераса (надзаливна тераса)	-
2	->->Високи тераси (IV-VI тераса, вис. до 100 м.)	-
2	->->Ниски тераси (I-III тераса, вис. до 40 м.)	-
2	->->Отстъп на речната тераса	-
2	->->Ръб на речната тераса (вежда, външен край)	-
2	->->Същинска тераса	-
2	->->Тил на речната тераса	-
0	Рид, вододелен рид	-
1	->Било на рид	-
1	->Връх на рид	-
1	->Език на рид	-
1	->Седловина	-
1	->Склон на рид	-
2	->->Горна част на склона	-
2	->->Долна част на склона	-
2	->->Площадка на склона	-
2	->->Подножие на склона	-

Level	Name (Bulgarian)	Name (English)
2	->->Склоново стъпало	-
2	->->Средна част на склона	-
0	Ровина	-
0	Свлачище	-
0	Сипей	-
0	Скален навес	-
0	Старица	-
0	Твърдица (остатъчно възвишение)	-

TERRAIN USAGE (linear)

Буклучища и бунища	
Гори и горски насаждения	
Други	
Ливади и пасища	
Насипване на хумусен слой	
Рудни и нерудни разработки	
Селскостопански култури	
Стационарни мелиоративни	
Строителство	
Трайни насаждения	

OWNERSHIP (linear - land ownership)

Други	Other
Държавна	National
Комбинирана	Combined
Кооперативна	Cooperative
На обществени организации	NGO
Общинска	Local authority
Смесена	Mixed
Частна	Private

ACCESSIBILITY

Достъпен	Accessible
Недостъпен	Inaccessible
Ограничена достъпност	Limited accessibility

OBSERVABILITY

Неограничена	Full
Ограничена	Limited

SLOPE

Голям - над 20°	High (more than 20°)
Малък - от 0-5°	Small (less than 5°)
Скален откос	Ridge
Среден - от 5-20°	Moderate (5-20°)

CONCENTRATION (of findings)

Голяма - над 5 находки на кв. м	High concentration (more than 5 findings per square meter).
Малка - 1 находка на кв. М	Small concentration (less than 1 finding per square meter).
Средна - до 5 нах.на кв. М	Moderate concentration (1-5 findings per square meter).

GROUPING (of findings)

Едноцентрична концентрация	Monocentric concentration
Многоцентрична концентрация	Multicentric concentration
Равномерно разпръснати находки	Equally distributed findings

8.4 Appendix D / MiBACT-ICCU

SITAR: ORIGINI DELL'INFORMAZIONE/SOURCE OF INFORMATION (acronym OI): the administrative and scientific information

ORIGINAL NAME	TRANSLATION	DESCRIPTION
Codice SITAR dell'OI	OI_ID SITAR	Unique numeric code assigned to each Source of Information that is stored in the SITAR geodatabase.
Sezione degli elementi spaziali identificativi della OI		Section on the identifying spatial elements of the OI
Geometria (multi-poligono)	Geometry (multi-polygon)	Spatialized field in which plain coordinates of the OI research areas are archived
Comune	Town/municipality	Official name corresponding to Agenzia del Territorio (italian cadastral agency) and ISTAT (italian statistical agency) code of Municipality.
Ripartizione Amministrativa	Administrative subdivision	This multiple field supports the references to the administrative subdivisions of Rome and Fiumicino. Rome's municipality consists of the 15 sub-municipalities (municipi). Fiumicino is a third-order administrative division structured in six topographical/urban zone.
Zona topografica / Località	Topographical area / Locality	This multiple field supports the references to the topographical zone and place names (sometimes only indicative) related to the extents of each OI; the lexicon is now based on the official list of ISTAT (italian statistical agency) and shared with Municipalities.
Indirizzi toponomastici	Toponymic addresses	This multiple field supports the list of toponymic addresses (road / street, house number) mentioned in the supplied archival documentation related to each OI. The lexicon is based on official list supplied by Agenzia del Territorio (italian cadastral services institution) and shared with Municipalities.
Grado di Georeferenziazione	Degree of Georeferencing	This field expresses with a text value the degree of spatial localization of each OI as referred to SITAR data georeferencing internal process. The information is based on the cartographic positioning and other details available in the Archive. The lexicon to adopt is the following: certain, approximate, reconstructe.
Metodo di Georeferenziazione	Georeferencing method	It expresses the cartographic method and its specification, by which it was possible to make the georeferencing of the Source of information.
Archivio Caposaldi Topografici	Relevant topographic benchmarks	This multiple field supports the list of the topographic benchmarks related to each OI. Every benchmark is defined by an ID, its geographical coordinates, a conventional name and a point monograph in pdf format.

Sezione degli elementi spaziali identificativi della OI		Section on the identifying spatial elements of the OI
Grado della Rappresentazione	Degree of the representation	It expresses the level of realism of the cartographic representation of each Source of Information in the SITAR WebGIS. This field does not express, therefore, a reliability value but rather the maximum extension of each excavation, field research or territory study as currently known by the available documentation.
Sezione degli elementi identificativi della costituzione della OI		Section on the constitutive elements of the OI
Metodologie di Indagine applicate	Methodologies of the applied investigations	This multiple field supports the references to the type or types of archaeological and / or geotechnical investigations implemented for each Source of Information. Each method of investigation previously indicated in the OI form, then is associated by the user to one or more Archaeological Partition, to trace the methodological origin for each element of knowledge acquired and stored in SITAR.
Relazioni con altre Origini dell'Informazione	Archive of the relationships with other Sources of Information	This multiple field supports the list of the relationships between different Sources of Information.
Ente proprietario del set di dati dell'OI	Owner of the data set of OI	The field registers the organization or the legal entity that owns the scientific and legal property of the administrative and archaeological data of the Source of Information.
Funzionario Responsabile SSBAR attuale	Responsible officer of the SSBAR	Name and surname of the SSBAR functionary currently responsible for the administrative area in which falls the Source of information.
Zona amministrativa o Servizio specifico della SSBAR	Administrative area or SSBAR specific service	The field registers the "historical" information relating to the area or SSBAR specific territorial service in which the investigations/studies were carried out.
Responsabile scientifico, Curatori e Autori	Scientific curators and authors	This multiple field expresses the reference to one or more scientific responsible, curators and / or authors of the investigation/study.
Data avvio indagini	Start date of investigation	The date indicate the start of work of investigation on site or the generic date of start of inquiries within bibliographic, historical, cartographic documentation.
Data fine indagini	End date of the investigations	This is the date of end of the work of investigation on site or the generic date of completion of the research carried out within bibliographic, historical, cartographic documentation.
Soggetto richiedente	Requesting entity	This is the natural or legal person who has sent to SSBAR the request for permission for building works (or other reasons as scientific researches) to whom was followed the investigations.
Soggetto esecutore	Executor subject	This multiple field supports the references to the natural and/or legal persons who specifically have executed the field works as e.g. companies, technical units, etc.

Sezione degli elementi identificativi della costituzione della OI		Section on the constitutive elements of the OI
Proprietà immobiliare	Real estate	This field records the reference to the holder of the real estate cadastre in which the investigations were carried out and yielded the Source of Information.
Descrizione dei lavori	Description of work	Free text field in which to draw the main characteristics of the investigations by rapid and precise references to the number, type and possible spatial interaction between the different stages of the investigation (geological cores, trenches, geological remote sensing, excavation for sample surveys or extensive stratigraphic survey, etc.) and other salient elements.
Costo complessivo dei lavori	Total cost of the work	It means the total cost of the works in Euros referring to the whole project's cost of the architectural and urban planning in relation to whom the investigations were carried out and generated the Source of Information.
Costo complessivo delle ricerche geoarcheologiche	Total cost of the geoarchaeological research	The field gives the specific costs amount of scientific archaeological and/or geological consulting, laboratory analysis, other specialist consulting, detailed surveys, etc.
Sezione identificativa della collocazione in Archivio della OI e dei riferimenti agli Archivi esterni alla SSBAR		Section on the archival elements of the OI
Archivio di conservazione	Conservation archive	The field records the "Section" of the SSBAR Archives in which it finds the position of the document folder from which it was derived the Source of Information.
Riferimenti di archivio ai documenti scientifici ed amministrativi correlati	List of the archive references to the related scientific and administrative documents	Multiple field for archival references to all the scientific and administrative documents related to the Source of Information, preserved in the SSBAR or external Archives.
Sezione degli elementi di sintesi dei dati forniti dalla OI		Section on the syntetic archaeological data provided by the OI
Partizioni Archeologiche correlate	List of the related Archaeological Partitions	This multiple field is dedicated to the list of all the Archaeological Partitions correlated with the Source of Information, divided according to the different investigations methodologies (geological surveys, archaeological digs, bibliographic researches, etc..) applied within the OI .
Sezione dei riferimenti alla documentazione digitale della OI		Section on digital documentation of the OI
Collegamenti ipermediali ai documenti digitali	List of links to digital documents	Multiple field dedicated to the list of hypermedia links to the documents stored in the SITAR digital file system, that are part of the document folder of each Source of Information.
Bibliografia	Bibliography	Multiple field dedicated to the bibliographical references inserted according to the standard of the National Bibliographic Service Catalog (www.iccu.sbn.it).

Sezione dei riferimenti alla documentazione digitale della OI		Section on digital documentation of the OI
Note	Note	Free text field to report notes and observations about the Source of Information and the SITAR digitalization internal process.
Sezione Utenti		Section Users
Utente owner della scheda di Origine dell'Informazione	Owner User of the record of Origin Information	This value is implemented automatically by the system on the base of the user authentication process. This specific user owns the right to extend the authorization for <i>read / update / soft-delete / re-extend</i> permissions to other users.
Archivio utenti/permessi attivati sul record di Origine dell'Informazione	Users authorizations activated for the record of Origin Information	Multiple field dedicated to support the owner user in authorizing other users to <i>read / update / soft-delete / re-extend permissions to other users</i> for each OI record.

PARTIZIONE ARCHEOLOGICA / ARCHAEOLOGICAL PARTITION (acronym PA): the description of the archaeological findings

ORIGINAL NAME	TRANSLATION	DESCRIPTION
Codice SITAR della PA	PA_ID SITAR	Unique ID assigned by the system and used both in the catalogue and in the cartographic geoDB section to identify each PA element.
Sezione degli elementi identificativi della PA		Section on the identifying elements of the PA
Geometria (multi-poligono)	Geometry (multi-polygon)	Spatialized field in which plain coordinates of the PA various parts are archived
Dati relativi all'Unita' Archeologica / Complesso Archeologico cui l'elemento PA è stato già eventualmente referenziato	Identifying data of the Archaeological Unit / Archaeological Complex to whom the PA element has already been referenced	Summary of the key data for the Archaeological Unit or Archaeological Complex to whom is assigned an PA element. The recall of these data is supported by the foreign key pointing to SITAR ID of the Archaeological Unit/Complex of relevance.
Codice SITAR dell'Origine dell'Informazione	Sitar Code of the Source of Information	Foreign key that refers to the SITAR Code of the Source of Information from which derives the catalogued PA element.
Dati descrittivi relativi alla localizzazione spaziale	Descriptive data for spatial location	Summary of the descriptive data of geographical and administrative location of the Source of Information from which derives the PA catalogued element.

Sezione degli elementi identificativi della PA	Section on the identifying elements of the PA	
Tipo della PA	PA type	<p>It expresses the type of the PA. There is an associated controlled vocabulary:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - corpo di fabbrica / architectural body - partizione funzionale / functional partition - partizione cronologica / chronological partition - ipotesi ricostruttiva / reconstructive hypotesis - segmento / archaeological structure or stratigraphy fragment - elemento con valenza topografica / ancient topographical element - areale di fonte letteraria diretta / ancient literary source area - elemento di ipotesi ricostruttiva / reconstructive hypotesis element - unità funzionale / architectural functional unit - elemento strutturale / structural element - interfaccia di discontinuità o di degrado / phisical discontinuity or degradation interface - connessione / structural connection - intervento di consolidamento / conservative intervention - restauro strutturale contemporaneo / contemporary conservative intervention

Sezione degli elementi identificativi della PA	Section on the identifying elements of the PA	
Metodologia di acquisizione	Acquisition methodology	<p>The field indicates in a univocal way the methodology which enabled the acquisition of the PA in the process of cataloging. There is an associated controlled vocabulary pre-filtered on the strenght of one or more items pre-selected at the OI level by the data-entry user:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scavo estensivo / extended excavation - Saggio di scavo (per trincee, sondaggi, pozzetti, etc.) / trench or sample excavation - Restauri e consolidamenti / conservative interventions - Ricerca di superficie / field survey - Ricerche geognostiche invasive / invasive geophysical researches - Ricerche geognostica non invasive / not invasive geophysical survey - Telerilevamento / remote sensing - Ricerca bibliografica / Bibliografical research - Analisi di fonte letteraria classica / ancient literary source analysis - Analisi di fonte cartografica d'archivio (es.: cartografia storica, tecnica, tematica, elaborato di dettaglio, schizzo misurato, etc.) / archive cartographic source analysis - Analisi di fonte iconografica d'archivio (veduta, stampa, immagine fotografica, filmato, etc.) / archive iconographic source analysis - Studio monografico di Unità Archeologica / Monograph on single archaeological monument or complex

Sezione degli elementi identificativi della PA	Section on the identifying elements of the PA	
Definizione Oggettiva	Objective Definition	<p>It expresses the elementary material category to whom the PA refers. There is an associated controlled vocabulary:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fondazione / foundation - alzata / wall - rivestimenti parietali (per gli elementi decorativi di particolare rilievo) / decorated wall covers - orizzontamento (pavimentazioni, solai, coperture) / floor - rivestimenti pavimentali (per gli elementi decorativi di particolare rilievo) / decorated floors (as mosaic, <i>opus sectile</i>, etc.) - soglia (apertura architettonica) / threshold - collegamenti verticali (scale, rampe) / stairs, ramps - strutture (nel caso di ricorrenza di elementi verticali ed orizzontali nello stesso contesto schedato) / indistinct set of structures - materiali archeologici in superficie / surface sporadic evidences - elementi architettonici / architectural elements - elementi scultorei / sculptural elements - elementi epigrafici / epigraphic elements - cavità artificiale / artificial cave - cavità naturale / natural cave - taglio artificiale / pit - taglio naturale / natural cut - livelli contemporanei / contemporary land-fill layers - livello archeologico (stratigrafie con materiali archeologici) / archaeological stratigraphy layer - livello non antropico / geo-archaeological layer - substrati geologici (o litologie di base) / geological underlayer - area di fonte letteraria classica / ancient literary source area - zona di degrado / degradation interface

Sezione degli elementi identificativi della PA	Section on the identifying elements of the PA	
Definizione Specifica	Specific Definition	It expresses a more specialized value for the definition of the PA under examination. There is an associated controlled vocabulary (work in progress) and available at this link
Definizione Interpretativa	Interpretative Definition	It expresses a first level of interpretation of the ancient topography valence of the PA. There is an associated controlled vocabulary (work in progress) shared with the <i>Archeological Unit Specific Definition</i> field.
Denominazioni Convenzionali	Conventional Denominations	Multiple field dedicated to the conventional names, as reliable, as maybe outdated or refuted, that have been attributed to a PA element over the time and can be deducted by the available documents.
Grado di georeferenziazione	Degree of georeferencing	This field expresses with a text value the degree of spatial localization of each PA as referred to SITAR data georeferencing internal process. The information is based on the cartographic positioning and other details available in the Archive. The lexicon to adopt is the following: certain, approximate, reconstructe.
Metodo di georeferenziazione	Georeferencing method	It expresses the cartographic method and its specification, by which it was possible to make the georeferencing of the PA.
Grado della rappresentazione	Degree of representation	It expresses the level of realism of the cartographic representation of each PA in the SITAR WebGIS. This field does not express, therefore, a reliability value but rather the graphical detail of a PA archived in the SITAR geODB as currently known by the available documentation.
Sezione degli elementi descrittivi della PA	Section of the descriptive elements of the PA	
Descrizione	Description	Descriptive text field basically containing key items as e.g.: - objects synthetic description (e.g., <i>wall, road axis, rectangular room</i> , etc.); - name of relevance (e.g.: <i>diverticulum of the "Via Latina"</i>); - orientation (e.g. <i>SE-NW, oriented at 315°</i>); - other significant descriptive data.

Sezione degli elementi descrittivi della PA	Section of the descriptive elements of the PA	
Tecniche Edilizie	Technical building	Multiple field that supports the list of building techniques correlated to a PA, structured in four essential elements of information for each record: 1) the type of work (identified by a roman numeral); 2) the masonry section and the presence of elements (identified by a capital letter); 3) the shape and the equipment of the materials which determine the construction of a certain work, or designate the building techniques (identified by an treng numeral); 4) the characteristics of the nucleus (identified by a lowercase letter). For each of these items of information rhere are associated controlled vocabularies.
Punti altimetrici disponibili	Altimetric points available for a PA	Multiple field dedicated to the altimetric points registrered for each PA in the available scientific documentation.
Relazioni tra le PA	Relationships between the PA	Multiple field dedicated to the structural and stratigraphic relationships between two or more PA
Sezione degli elementi cronologici della PA	Section on the chronological elements of the PA	
Cronologia Specifica (Cronologia iniziale; Cronologia finale)	Specific Chronology (initial and final chronology)	This multiple field describes the overall chronology of a PA element specifically structured in simple consecutive chronological intervals (as e.g. "foundation chronology", "use/life chronology", "destruction chronology", etc.) provided with their respective time limits.
Cronologia Generale	General Chronology	It expresses a summary text string (also with respective numeric values) automatically compiled by the system on the trength of the oldest chronological interval (e.g. "Republic roman age") and the most recent interval set for a PA (e.g.: "Augustan age").
Periodo	Period	It indicates the belonging of a PA to a specific historical period.
Fase	Phase	The specific archaeological phase to whom a PA element is related on the trength of the available documentation.

Sezione degli elementi di sintesi dello stato di accessibilità e fruibilità	Section with the sintetic element of the state of accessibility and usability	
Accessibilità / fruibilità	Accessibility and usability	It expresses the actual status and the level of exploitation of a PA.
Sezione dei riferimenti alla documentazione digitale dell'elemento PA	Section with the references to the digital documentation of the PA	
Collegamenti ai files della documentazione digitale di dettaglio della PA	Links to the files of the detailed digitalized documentation of the PA	In this multiple field it is possible to archive the links to the files of the digitalized documentation of a PA.
Bibliografia correlata con la PA	List of the bibliographic records related to the PA element	Multiple field for bibliographic references available for each PA. The bibliographical references are inserted according to the standard of the National Bibliographic Service Catalog (www.iccu.sbn.it).
Sezione Utenti	Users section	
Utente	User	This value is implemented automatically by the system on the base of the user authentication process.
Archivio utenti/permessi attivati sul record di Partizione Archeologica	Users authorizations activated for the record of PA	Multiple field dedicated to support the owner user in authorizing other users to <i>read / update / soft-delete / re-extend permissions to other users</i> for each PA record.

UNITÀ ARCHEOLOGICA / ARCHAEOLOGICAL UNIT (UA): the scientific description of each archaeological complex or monument

ORIGINAL NAME	TRANSLATION	DESCRIPTION
ID_Unità Archeologica / Complesso Archeologico	SITAR ID of the Archaeological Unit / Archaeological Complex	ID automatically assigned by the system
Geometria (multi-poligono)	Geometry (multi-polygon)	Spatialized field in which plain coordinates of the UA total extent are archived
Sezione degli elementi identificativi dell'Unità Archeologica / Complesso Archeologico	Section with the elements that define the archaeological unit / monumental complex	
Codice univoco identificativo SITAR	SITAR identifier unique code	Unique code which allows the identification of each UA - CA that may be 'customized' by the user/cataloguer.
Codice univoco identificativo in MODI dell'ICCD (campo C.U.I.)	ICCD - MODI Unique Code Identifier (field "C.U.I.")	Alphanumeric code assigned by the Commission on the preventive archeology.
Codice SITAR dell'Origine dell'Informazione di afferenza	Sitar Code of the Source of Information	Foreign key that refers to the SITAR Code of the Source of Information from which derives the catalogued UA.

Sezione degli elementi identificativi dell'Unità Archeologica / Complesso Archeologico	Section with the elements that define the archaeological unit / monumental complex	
Dati descrittivi relativi alla localizzazione spaziale	Descriptive data for spatial location	Summary of the descriptive data of geographical and administrative location of the Source of Information corresponding to the monograph study of the catalogued UA.
Tipo dell'UA	UA type	It indicates the type of catalogued UA. There is an associated controlled vocabulary (work in progress): - Archaeological Unit - Archaeological Complex - Monumental Complex - Architectural Archifact
Definizione oggettiva dell'UA	Objective definition of the UA	It expresses the functional category of the UA. There is an associated controlled vocabulary (work in progress based on ICCD - MA/CA vocabulary) that automatically maps each Objective Definition item (e.g. "villa") with a general functional category ("private settlement") and a type of space use (<i>public</i> vs. <i>private</i>). The vocabulary is available at this web link .
Definizione specifica (denominazione convenzionale corrente del monumento o complesso archeologico)	Specific definition (as current conventional of the UA if it is a well known monument or complex)	It expresses a value more specialized than objective definition that completes the current conventional name for the UA in case of well known monument or complex. There is an associated controlled lexicon that basically corresponds to the Lexicon Topographicum Urbis Romae with due updates and revisions (for Fiumicino territory the work is still in progress).
Altre denominazioni convenzionali	Other conventional names	Multiple field that supports the references to one or more conventional names attributed by ancient sources, researchers or even oral tradition, that could be obtained thanks to the available documentation of the UA.
Grado di georeferenziazione	Degree of georeferencing	This field expresses with a text value the degree of spatial localization of each UA as referred to SITAR data georeferencing internal process. The information is based on the cartographic positioning and other details available in the Archive. The lexicon to adopt is the following: certain, approximate, reconstructed.
Metodo di georeferenziazione	Georeferencing method	It expresses the cartographic method and its specification, by which it was possible to make the georeferencing of the UA.

Sezione degli elementi identificativi dell'Unità Archeologica / Complesso Archeologico	Section with the elements that define the archaeological unit / monumental complex	
Grado della rappresentazione	Degree of representation	It expresses the level of realism of the cartographic representation of each UA in the SITAR WebGIS. This field does not express, therefore, a reliability value but rather the graphical detail of a UA archived in the SITAR geODB as currently known by the available documentation.
Sezione degli elementi descrittivi dell'UA	Section with the descriptive elements of the UA	
Descrizione	Description	Pre-formatted field with the key items that are strictly necessary for the description of the UA as e.g.: - synthetic description of buildings blocks and architectural bodies, functional parts, etc.; - orientation of architectural and urban axis; - other significant descriptive data.
Tecniche edilizie	Building techniques	Data on building techniques recognized in different parts of the UA. The records are structured as in PA related building techniques.
Relazioni tra ua/ca	Relationships between UA	Multiple field that supports the list of topographic and chronological relationships that exist between two or more UA.
Punti altimetrici	Altimetric points available for a UA	Multiple field dedicated to the altimetric points registered for each UA in the available scientific documentation.
Sezione degli elementi cronologici dell'UA	Section of chronological elements of the UA	
Cronologia Specifica (Cronologia iniziale; Cronologia finale)	Specific Chronology (initial and final chronology)	This multiple field describes the overall chronology of a UA specifically structured in simple consecutive chronological intervals (as e.g. "foundation chronology", "use/life chronology", "destruction chronology", etc.) provided with their respective time limits.
Cronologia Generale	General Chronology	It expresses a summary text string (also with respective numeric values) automatically compiled by the system on the strenght of the oldest chronological interval (e.g. "Republic roman age") and the most recent interval set for a UA (e.g.: "Augustan age").
Periodo	Period	It indicates the belonging of a UA to a specific historical period.
Fase	Phase	The specific archaeological phase to whom a UA is related on the strenght of the available documentation.

Sezione degli elementi di sintesi dello stato di accessibilità e fruibilità	Section with the sintetic element of the state of accessibility and usability	
Accessibilità / fruibilità	Accessibility / usability	It expresses the actual status and the level of exploitation of an UA.
Sezione dei riferimenti alla documentazione digitale dell'UA	Section with the references to the digital documentation of the UA	
Collegamenti ai files della documentazione digitale di dettaglio dell'UA	Links to the files of the detailed digitalized documentation of the UA	In this multiple field it is possible to archive the links to the files of the digitalized documentation of a UA.
Bibliografia correlata con la UA	List of the bibliographic records related to the UA	Multiple field for bibliographic references available for each UA. The bibliographical references are inserted according to the standard of the National Bibliographic Service Catalog (www.iccu.sbn.it).
Note	Notes	Text field for notes
Sezione Utenti	Section Users	
Utente proprietario e validatore	Owner and validator User	The SSBAR Functionary that is responsible to create the UA record and can validate the information entered. This user is also the owner of the record and can extend rights of <i>read / update / soft-delete / re-extend permission</i> to other specific users.
Utente schedatore	Cataloguer User	User who enters the descriptive data and cartographic data related to an UA.

DISPOSITIVI DI TUTELA / LAW CONSTRAINT DECREES (DT): the law-constraints which punctually preserves each complex and/or monument

ORIGINAL NAME	TRANSLATION	DESCRIPTION
Codice SITAR DT	SITAR ID of the DT	ID automatically assigned by the system
Geometria (multi-poligono)	Geometry (multi-polygon)	Spatialized field in which plain coordinates of the DT different areas (distinguished by conservation type: <i>direct</i> or <i>indirect</i>) are archived
Sezione dei dati identificativi del DT	Section on the identifying data of the DT	
Numero di scheda DT dell'Ufficio Vincoli	Code of DT assigned by Ufficio Vincoli della SSBAR (specific internal office)	Previous alphanumeric code assigned by SSBAR internal office in charge of DT management
Denominazione Convenzionale del DT	Conventional name fo DT	Text field containing the SSBAR conventional name of DT often containing the conventional name of UA protected by the DT
Tipo del dispositivo di tutela	DT Type	Field for the basic type of DT supported by a controlled vocabulary based on current italian law enacting types (e.g. <i>Decreto ministeriale, Decreto del Direttore regionale, Disposizioni del Soprintendente</i> , etc.)

Sezione dei dati identificativi del DT		Section on the identifying data of the DT	
Data di emissione	Issue date of DT	Date field relevant to the official issue of the DT	
Normativa di riferimento	Relevant legislation	This field express the reference to the relevant legislation on which the DT issued has been based	
Tipo di vincolo imposto	Law constraint type	This field express the conservation environment to which the DT is related. Ther is an associated controlled vocabulary referred to: - archaeological law constraint - monumental law constraint - landscape law constraint	
Tipo di tutela imposta (diretta, indiretta)	Conservation type	This field express the conservation type through the DT application	
Tipo di bene archeologico tutelato	Monument/complex protected by the DT	Monument / complex type protected by the DT. The recall of these data is supported by the foreign key pointing to SITAR ID of the Archaeological Unit/Complex protected by the DT.	
Funzionario Responsabile SSBAR attuale	Responsible officer of the SSBAR	Name and surname of the SSBAR functionary currently responsible for the administrative area in which falls the DT.	
Sezione degli elementi spaziali identificativi del DT		Section on the identifying spatial elements of the DT	
Ripartizione Amministrativa	Administrative subdivision	This multiple field supports the references to the administrative subdivisions of Rome and Fiumicino. Rome's municipality consists of the 15 sub-municipalities (municipi). Fiumicino is a third-order administrative division structured in six topographical/urban zone.	
Zona topografica / Località	Topographical area / Locality	This multiple field supports the references to the topographical zone and place names (sometimes only indicative) related to the extents of each DT; the lexicon is now based on the official list of ISTAT (talian statistical agency) and shared with Municipalities.	
Indirizzi toponomastici	Toponymic addresses	This multiple field supports the list of toponymic addresses (road / street, house number) mentioned in the supplied archival documentation related to each DT. The lexicon is based on official list supplied by Agenzia del Territorio (talian cadastral services institution) and shared with Municipalities.	

Sezione delle note procedurali del DT	Section on the procedural notes of the OI	
Note sulla procedura del DT	Notes on the DT	Text field for procedural notes on the DT current legal situation
Note sui ricorsi giuridici avverso il DT	Legal appeals towards the DT	Text field for references to legal appeals towards the DT issue promoted by private or public owners of immovables subject to DT
Sezioni di dati catastali, amministrativi e anagrafici correlati con il DT	Sections with the references to the cadastral, administrative and personal data related to the DT	
Lista degli immobili vincolati dal DT	List of immovables subject to the DT	In this multiple field it is possible to archive the references to the cadastral data of immovables subject to DT
Pratiche di Tutela correlate con il DT	Administrative procedures related to DT	In this multiple field it is possible to archive the references to the administrative procedures related to the DT issue
Lista dei proprietari degli immobili vincolati	List of owners of immovables subject to DT	In this multiple field it is possible to archive the references to the personal data of private and public owners of immovables subject to DT
Note di trascrizione delle pratiche di tutela	Transcription deeds of the DT	In this multiple field it is possible to archive the references to the transcription deeds of the DT at local public real estate registry (c.s. <i>Conservatorie dei Registri Immobiliari</i>)
Sezione dei riferimenti alla documentazione digitale del DT	Section with the references to the digital documentation of the DT	
Documenti digitali allegati al DT	Links to the files of the detailed digitalized documentation of the DT	In this multiple field it is possible to archive the links to the files of the digitalized documentation of a DT.

8.5 Appendix E / INRAP

DOLIA: The metadata schema is UNIMARC compliant

Block	
001	
010 (a,b,d)	International Standard Book Number (ISBN)
011 (a,d)	ISSN
100 (a)	General Processing Data
101 (a,c)	Language of the Ressource
102 (a,b)	Country of Publication or Production
105 (a)	Coded Data Field : Textual Language Materiel, Monographic
110 (a)	Coded Data Field: Continuing Resources
200 (a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h,i,v,z,5)	Title and Statement of Responsibility
205 (a,f,g)	Edition Statement
207 (ind2,a)	Material Specific Area: Continuing Resources – Numbering
210 (a,c,d,5)	Publication, Distribution, etc
215 (a,c,d,e)	Physical Description
225 (a,f,v, x)	Series
230 (a)	Material Specific Area: Electronic Resource Characteristics
300 (a)	General Note
304 (a)	Notes Pertaining to Title and Statement of Responsibility
320 (a)	Internal Bibliographies/Indexes Note
326 (a,b)	Frequency Statement Note (Continuing Resources)
327 (a)	Contents Note
330 (a)	Summary or Abstract
345 (a,b,c,d)	Acquisition Information Note
410 (t,v,x)	Series
451 (ind2,t,x,y,0,3,5)	Other Edition in the Same Medium
452 (u,t,0)	Edition in a Different Medium
461 (a,d,e,p,t,v,0,5)	Set level
463 (a,d,e,p,t,v,0,5)	Piece Level
464 (ind2, t, 3, 5)	Piece-Analytic Level
470 (ind2,t,y,3,5)	Item reviewed
488 (a,t,0,5)	Other Related Works

Block	
510 (a)	Parallel Title Prope
531 (a)	Abbreviated Title (Continuing Resources)
532 (ind1,ind2,a,z)	Expanded Title
541 (ind1,ind2,a,z)	Expanded Title
606 (5)	Subject Thesaurus
607 (5)	Places Thesaurus
610 (ind1,a)	Uncontrolled Subject Terms
631 (5)	People Thesaurus
634 (5)	Chronology Thesaurus
641 (a)	Candidate descriptor (People thesaurus)
644 (a)	Candidate descriptor (Chronology thesaurus)
645 (a)	Candidate descriptor (Places thesaurus)
646 (a)	Candidate descriptor (Subject thesaurus)
700 (a,b,p)	Personnal Name- Primary Responsibility
701 (a,b,p)	Personal Name – Alternative Responsibility
702 (a,b)	Personnal Name – Secondary Responsibility
710 (a,g,h,p)	Corporate Body Name – Primary Responsibility
711 (a,g,p)	Corporate Body Name – Alternative Responsibility
712 (a,d,e,f,g)	Corporate Body Name – Secondary Responsibility
801 (a,b,e)	Originating Source
830 (a)	General Cataloguer's Note
856 (ind1,d,e,u)	Electronic Location and Access

8.6 Appendix F – Questionnaire on datasets, metadata and data sharing policies

Partner name: _____ **Contact:** _____

This form will be filled-in by each content provider with information describing the content of each dataset and its metadata.

DATASET

1. Dataset name

2. Dataset description - Provide a short description. If the dataset is a collection of several archives, please provide collection information only.

3. Subjects – provide general subject keywords

4. Geographic coverage – the areas or regions covered

5. Temporal coverage – the archaeological or historical time periods covered

6. Content - E.g. Text, image, movie, sound, music etc

7. Language of the content if applicable - E.g. for text documents, multimedia resources with audio

8. Format of the content - E.g. JPEG, MPEG, Quicktime, HTML, PDF etc.

9. Number of items - E.g. 1000 film clips, 2 million pages, 20,000 books etc.

METADATA - Describe fields, languages and structure of the metadata, including any access restriction.

10. Metadata schema - Describe the fields, proprietary/conforms to standard/is mapped to a standard, name any relevant standards

11. Use of standard vocabularies

12. Metadata language(s)

RIGHT AND ACCESS

13. Rights holder(s) - The owner(s) of the rights of the content being provided

14. Content copyright - Describe the copyright of the content in the dataset being provided – is there a standard rights framework (e.g. Creative Commons licences), or many individual copyrights?

15. Content Access rights - Describe the access rights to use the content in the ARIADNE project, e.g.: public access, restricted to registered users, open to consortium members for research, etc.

16. If you have a standard access or licence agreement for your **content**, please provide a link/copy. Can you provide a copy of your access/licence agreement in English?

17. Metadata rights – can metadata be made available to ARIADNE under CC0 or a Public Domain licence to enable linked open data? Yes/No

18. Describe the metadata rights and any access restrictions, e.g. to specific elements.

19. Online availability – give the URI/URL
